

A reclamation protocol for water reuse in craft beer production

Deliverable 2.8

A reclamation protocol for water reuse in craft beer production

Deliverable 2.8

Summary

To build the society's trust and acceptance of water reuse and anticipating solutions for mitigating future scenarios of more severe water scarcity, the Lisbon living lab innovation actions included a pilot demonstration of water reclamation for artisanal beer production to provide scientific evidence on the safety of direct potable reuse in industry. Deliverable (D) 2.8 proposes a protocol for water reclamation aiming at water reuse in craft beer production. It includes (i) a discussion of the three key components/dimensions, regulatory, technical, and public outreach, of direct potable reuse for craft beer production, and (ii) an analysis of the multi-barrier approach needed for safe direct potable reuse for craft beer production, the Critical Control Points, and the monitoring, based on the results and lessons learned from the pilot demonstration conducted in Beirolas Water Resource Recovery Facility, in the B-WaterSmart Lisbon Living Lab.

Deliverable number	Work package
D2.8	WP2.4.1
Lead beneficiary	Milestone author(s)
AdTA	David Figueiredo, Rita Lourinho (AdTA) Rui Viegas, Elsa Mesquita, Maria João Rosa (LNEC)
Quality assurance	
LNEC CETAQUA	Catarina Silva Eric Santos
Planned delivery date	Actual delivery date
29/02/2024	31/05/2024 19/11/2024 (revised version)

Dissemination level

- PU = Public
- PP = Restricted to other programme participants
- RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium.
Please specify: _____
- CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium

Date	Change
31/05/2024	Initial version
October 2024	<p data-bbox="416 329 517 353">Version 2:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <li data-bbox="416 365 791 389">• The Table of contents was revised. <li data-bbox="416 400 756 425">• The List of Figures was revised. <li data-bbox="416 436 748 461">• The List of Tables was revised. <li data-bbox="416 472 1182 497">• In the Executive summary, the changes regarding chapter 4 were included. <li data-bbox="416 508 1310 566">• In section 4.3.1, a paragraph discussing the LRVs achieved by each treatment scheme is discussed and compared with indicative values. <li data-bbox="416 577 1390 636">• Under section 4.3 (“Monitoring results of the pilot unit”), a new section (4.3.3) entitled “Overall results of water quality towards beer production” was added. <li data-bbox="416 647 1390 705">• In section 4.3.3 (new), a sentence regarding the remineralization of the RO produced waters for beer production was introduced. <li data-bbox="416 716 1374 775">• In section 4.3.3 (new), a paragraph discussing the residual concentration of trace organics was included. <li data-bbox="416 786 1358 844">• In section 4.3.3 (new), a paragraph discussing NDMA potential formation during the brewing process was introduced. <li data-bbox="416 855 1398 936">• To enhance the clarity of Section 4.4 (“Main conclusions from this specific demo”), it was divided into 3 sub-sections: 4.4.1 – “Water quality towards beer production”, 4.4.2 – “Treatment trains” and 4.4.3 – “Operation protocol”. <li data-bbox="416 947 1350 1005">• In section 4.4.2 (new), a paragraph discussing the not so high water recovery rates achieved during the demo was added. <li data-bbox="416 1016 1366 1097">• In section 4.4.2 (new), two tables (Table 4.4 and Table 4.5) comparing the main analytical and operational results of the four treatment trains studied was included and a discussion is presented. <li data-bbox="416 1108 1398 1279">• In section 4.4.3 (new), the discussion was revised and we conclude that scheme 2 (comprising ultrafiltration with post-chlorination, reverse osmosis) exhibits the best performance for this specific pilot demonstration. Accordingly, this conclusion was included in the Executive summary and in the conclusions chapter (new) as “the scheme comprising UF (+ Cl₂, whenever needed for RO biofouling control) + RO should be adequate for this specific application”. <li data-bbox="416 1290 1382 1348">• In section 4.4.3 (new), a discussion of how to address the brine stream produced from RO was introduced. <li data-bbox="416 1359 895 1384">• A conclusions section was added (Chapter 6). <li data-bbox="416 1395 1286 1453">• New references were added in Chapter 7 – References (renumbered from Chapter 6–References). <li data-bbox="416 1464 1366 1523">• A summary of all analytical results was included in annex (ANNEX I – Summary of all analytical results).

Table of contents

List of Figures	V
List of Tables	VI
List of acronyms and abbreviations	VII
1 Introduction	4
1.1 Context	4
1.1.1 International, European and Portuguese context	4
1.1.2 Lisbon context	5
1.1.3 B-WaterSmart context and water reuse in beer production	5
1.2 Indirect and direct potable reuse	6
1.3 Scope, objectives and document structure	7
2 Regulation and health-based targets	9
2.1 Applicable or related regulations	9
2.2 Water quality targets.....	9
3 Critical parameters and control points	12
3.1 System description.....	12
3.1.1 Beirolas WRRF	12
3.1.2 Pilot unit.....	14
3.2 Hazards	16
3.2.1 General principles.....	16
3.2.2 Microbiological hazards	16
3.2.3 Chemical hazards	17
3.3 Hazards control	17
3.3.1 General principles.....	17
3.3.2 Control measures / multi-barrier approach	18
3.3.3 Validation of control measures	19
4 Monitoring: field results and recommendations	21
4.1 Water quality monitoring in the pilot study	21
4.1.1 Sampling points.....	21
4.1.2 Microbiological parameters	21
4.1.3 Chemical parameters	22
4.2 Operational monitoring in the pilot study	23
4.3 Monitoring results of the pilot unit.....	25
4.3.1 Microbiological water quality results	25
4.3.2 Chemical water quality results	25
4.3.3 Operational results	30
4.4 Main conclusions from this specific demo.....	32

4.4.1	Water quality towards beer production.....	32
4.4.2	Potable reuse schemes	32
4.4.3	Operation protocol	35
5	Management and communication.....	38
5.1	Incident protocols.....	38
5.2	Reviewing of incidents protocols	39
5.3	Communication	39
6	Conclusions.....	40
7	References	41
	ANNEX I – Summary of all analytical results	45

List of Figures

Figure 3.1 – View of Beirolas WRRF, Map location of Beirolas WRRF.....	12
Figure 3.2 – Beirolas WRRF water reuse treatment lines.	13
Figure 3.3 – Pilot unit installed at Beirolas WRRF and group photo during the NTNU visit in November 2022.....	14
Figure 3.4 – Pilot unit system diagram.	15
Figure 3.5 – Potable reuse schemes tested and demonstrated in the pilot unit at Beirolas WRRF.	19
Figure 3.6 – Critical control points in the potable reuse schemes.....	20
Figure 4.1 – Water quality monitoring sampling points.....	21
Figure 4.2 – Operational monitoring points of the pilot unit.....	23
Figure 4.3 – PFAS concentrations throughout scheme 1 and removal rates.	26
Figure 4.4 – PFAS concentrations throughout scheme 2 and removal rates.	26
Figure 4.5 – PFAS concentrations throughout scheme 3 and removal rates.	26
Figure 4.6 – PFAS concentrations throughout scheme 4 and removal rates.	27
Figure 4.7 – PhC concentrations throughout scheme 1 and removal rates.	27
Figure 4.8 – PhC concentrations throughout scheme 2 and removal rates.	28
Figure 4.9 – PhC concentrations throughout scheme 3 and removal rates.	28
Figure 4.10 – PhC concentrations throughout scheme 4 and removal rates.....	29
Figure 4.11 – NDMA concentration throughout potable reuse schemes and removal rates.....	29
Figure 4.12 – HAA concentrations throughout scheme 2 and removal rates.	30
Figure 4.13 – RO feed pressure during the demonstration.	30
Figure 4.14 – RO feed electrical conductivity during the demonstration.....	31
Figure 4.15 – RO net driving pressure during the demonstration.	31
Figure 4.16 – Potable reuse scheme 2 configuration.....	36

List of Tables

Table 2.1 – Microbiological targets, parameters and indicators based on DWD 2020.....	9
Table 2.2 – Chemical targets, parameters and indicators based on DWD 2020..	10
Table 3.1 – Quality requirements for Beirolas WRRF effluent and reclaimed water for internal and external uses.....	13
Table 3.2 – Average quality of Beirolas WWRF effluent and of reclaimed water for external uses - Class A, during 2023.....	13
Table 4.1 – Microbiological parameters included in the monitoring plan.	22
Table 4.2 – Chemical parameters included in the monitoring plan.....	22
Table 4.3 – Operational monitoring points, associated parameters of the pilot unit.....	24
Table 4.4 – Comparison of the main analytical results of the four potable reuse schemes studied.....	33
Table 4.5 – Comparison of the main RO operational results of the four potable reuse schemes studied.	35
Table 4.6 – Summary of key operating conditions and operational guidelines recommended for the treatment processes studied.....	37

List of acronyms and abbreviations

A254	Absorbance at 254 nm
A436	Absorbance at 436 nm
AdTA	Águas do Tejo Atlântico, S.A.
BAC	Biologically Active Granular Activated Carbon
BDCA	Bromodichloroacetic Acid
BOD5	5-day Biochemical Oxygen Demand
CA	Chloroacetic Acid
CCP	Critical Control Point
CIP	Cleaning In Place
COD	Chemical Oxygen Demand
DBAA	Dibromoacetic Acid
DBP	Disinfection Byproduct
DL	Decree-Law
DOC	Dissolved Organic Carbon
DPD	N, N-diethyl-p-phenylenediamine
DPR	Direct Potable Reuse
DWD	Drinking Water Directive
EBCT	Empty Bed Contact Time
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GAC	Granular Activated Carbon
H2020	Horizon 2020
HAA	Haloacetic acid
IPR	Indirect Potable Reuse
LL	Living Lab
LNEC	Laboratório Nacional de Engenharia Civil, I.P.
LOQ	Limit of Quantification
LRV	Log Reduction Value
MBAA	Monobromoacetic Acid
NDMA	N-Nitrosodimethylamine
NDP	Net Driving Pressure
ORP	Oxidation-Reduction Potential
PFOA	Perfluorooctanoic Acid
PFAS	Per- and Polyfluoroalkyl Substances
PFOSA	Perfluorooctanesulfonamide
PFOS	Perfluorooctane Sulfonate
PhC	Pharmaceutical Compound
RO	Reverse Osmosis
SD	Standard deviation
SUVA	Specific Ultraviolet Absorbance
TCA	Trichloroacetic Acid
TDS	Total Dissolved Solids
THM	Trihalomethane
TN	Total Nitrogen
TOC	Total Organic Carbon
TP	Total Phosphorus
UF	Ultrafiltration
USFDA	United States Food and Drug Administration
UWWTD	Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive
WFD	Water Framework Directive
WP	Work Package
WRR	Water Recovery Rate
WRRF	Water Resource Recovery Facility

Executive summary

To encourage the adoption of urban water reuse in Lisbon and facilitate its replication in other national and international cities, generating and sharing knowledge is crucial. One of the most significant initiatives supporting this effort is Lisbon's role as one of the six Living Labs (LLs) within B-WaterSmart. The Lisbon Living Lab aims to (i) in the short term, promote water and related energy and phosphorus efficiency, water-smart allocation (fit-for-purpose quality), circular economy practices, and safe non-potable urban water reuse; and (ii) in the mid to long term, demonstrate the potential for safe potable water reuse in the beverage industry.

Potable reuse can provide a realistic and practical source of drinking water under various circumstances and pilot demonstration projects are essential for developing future guidelines and best practices. The work conducted within task 2.4.1 of the B-WaterSmart project aims to contribute with pilot field data to the development of such guidelines, focusing on water quality and reclamation schemes' operation and redundancy for the safe production, from municipal wastewater, of water with adequate quality to be used in craft beer production. This involves direct potable reuse (DPR) applications with additional downstream safety barriers (provided by the beer production steps). The goal is to establish DPR as a solution for aggravated water scarcity, localized needs, emergency situations, and to build societal trust in water reuse safety.

A pilot unit was installed at the Beirolas Water Resource Recovery Facility (WRRF) in Portugal, one of the largest in the country (213,510 p.e. design capacity), with tertiary treatment (carbon and nutrients removal) and sand filtration. Four advanced treatment technologies were pilot tested – ultrafiltration (UF), ozonation (O₃), biologically active granular activated carbon (BAC) filtration, and reverse osmosis (RO), under the following operating conditions:

- **Ozonation:** 1-2 mg O₃/mg TOC, with 45 minutes contact time.
- **BAC filtration:** approximately 5 minutes empty bed contact time (EBCT), operated for 31 kBV (bed volumes);
- **Reverse osmosis:** 3-stage RO (2:1:1) with 8-12 bar net driving pressure, 15-25 L/(m².h) permeate flux, 60-70% water recovery rate, concentrate recirculation, and 3 mg/L antiscalant dosing.

In some schemes, chlorine (Cl₂) was dosed (in low concentrations, 0.9 mg Cl₂/L) to prevent biofouling of the RO membranes. The pilot unit was housed in a containerized unit with external cork coating and photovoltaic energy production. To compare different RO-based reclamation schemes regarding water quality and operational performance, four treatment schemes were continuously piloted (24/7):

1. **UF + O₃ + RO**
2. **UF (+ Cl₂) + RO**
3. **UF (+ Cl₂) + O₃ + BAC + RO**
4. **O₃ + BAC + RO**

System integrity monitoring included online UF and RO flow rate, pressure, and turbidity, as well as RO pH and electrical conductivity. Water quality was regularly analysed (weekly) for parameters such as *E. coli*, organic matter (TOC/DOC, A254, A436, SUVA), NH₄, NO₃, KN, TN, P, hardness, and alkalinity. Additionally, trace compounds were analysed once per treatment scheme, including 54 pharmaceutical compounds (PhCs), 2 hormones, oxidation by-products (N-nitrosodimethylamine (NDMA), bromate, chlorate), 4 trihalomethanes (THMs), 9 haloacetic acids (HAAs), 20 per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS), 10 alkylphenols, and toxicity indicators (*Daphnia magna*, *Vibrio fischeri*). The analyses also covered parameters specified in the EU Drinking Water Directive 2020/2184 (DWD 2020) and pathogen indicators of enteric bacteria (*Clostridium perfringens*), enteric

viruses (somatic coliphages/F-specific RNA bacteriophages), and protozoa (*Clostridium perfringens* spores).

All four multi-barrier treatment schemes produced water of sufficient quality to be reused in the beverage industry, complying with EU and Portuguese drinking water standards. Pathogen indicators were absent, and levels of PFAS, disinfection byproducts, and pharmaceutical compounds were mostly below the quantification limits (PFAS < 0.3, 0.6, 1 or 2 ng/L, 5 HAAs < 1 µg/L, bromate < 3 µg/L, chlorate < 8 µg/L, chlorite < 5 µg/L, PhCs < 0.1 to 1.2 µg/L). Total THMs varied between < 0.5 µg/L (LOQ) and 1.8 µg/L (far below the DWD 2020 parametric value) and NDMA was below the international guidelines.

Key findings include:

- **UF ensured complete disinfection of its permeate;**
- **Ozone effectively oxidized some inorganic and organic chemicals;**
- **BAC filtration removed certain dissolved chemicals;**
- **RO reduced all dissolved chemicals to below their LOQ (except NDMA), including oxidation by-products and recalcitrant dissolved compounds.**

Operational monitoring results indicated lower normalized net driving pressure, i.e. lower energy demand, for the potable reuse scheme comprising only UF (+ low dose Cl₂) and RO. Thus, considering the results obtained and the downstream safety barriers provided by the beer production steps (including boiling) for controlling pathogens and volatile dissolved chemicals (WHO and the State Water Resources Control Board of California recommend a multibarrier approach), the scheme comprising UF (+ Cl₂, whenever needed for RO biofouling control) + RO should be adequate for this specific application. In cases where the water is to be stored, an artificial buffer (engineered storage buffer) should be foreseen and, depending on the storage time and conditions, a final addition of a residual disinfectant, e.g. chlorine, may be needed to assure the microbiological stability of the reclaimed water (avoid microbial regrowth), which would further act as an additional barrier.

Based on the results obtained, the following indicators are recommended for regular monitoring (weekly and/or monthly) to streamline water quality monitoring and control hazards in the potable reuse scheme:

- **Coliform bacteria or *Escherichia coli* and *Clostridium perfringens*** as indicators for enteric bacteria, ***Clostridium perfringens* spores** as an indicator for protozoa, **somatic coliphages and bacteriophages** as indicators for viruses, with the primary removal mechanism being the RO process;
- **Dissolved organic carbon (DOC)** as an indicator of dissolved organics, useful for informing on the removal performance of unknown or emerging contaminants and for adjusting the treatment operating conditions;
- **Electrical conductivity** to ensure the effectiveness of the reverse osmosis process in removing inorganic compounds and emerging contaminants, the lower the better the RO effectiveness and the treated water quality.

Regarding the water quality monitoring, it is recommended to monitor the parameters outlined in the Drinking Water Directive 2020, which, for safety and risk mitigation, it is advised to sample 12 times in the first year of operation (monthly in case of a regular production or seasonally representative). After the first year, the results should be analysed to determine an appropriate new sampling frequency. This same frequency is proposed for monitoring other contaminants such as pharmaceutical compounds or NDMA. Further, key operating conditions and operational guidelines are recommended for the treatment processes regarding ozonation, GAC/BAC and RO.

Also, effective management and communication are critical for potable reuse schemes, which require skilled personnel to handle routine operations and emergencies. Incident and emergency response

protocols must be planned, coordinated and regularly tested through mock scenarios. For potable reuse in craft beer production, protocols should align with general drinking water safety plans but consider specific wastewater characteristics and be regularly reviewed and updated, as necessary, based on incident evaluations. Incident protocols need to outline procedures and responsibilities for various incident types, assess severity, report requirements, document responses, and involve stakeholders like the wastewater utility, the beer producer and competent authorities.

1 Introduction

1.1 Context

1.1.1 International, European and Portuguese context

In line with the United Nations' 2030 Sustainable Development Goals and their targets, the water sector faces significant challenges concerning the sustainability of this scarce resource. These challenges are connected to climate change, which affects the frequency and duration of extreme weather events, like the growing incidence of heavy rainfall alternating with prolonged droughts (IPCC, 2014). Moreover, between 2014 and 2050 the world population is expected to increase by 33% from 7.2 billion to 9.6 billion (UNDESA, 2014). This projection means that the percentage of people living in urban areas will increase from 54% to 66%, with urbanization in 89 countries expected to exceed 80% (UNDESA, 2014).

Climate change and climate variability are intensifying droughts and flooding, increasing pressure on water resources. Currently, water scarcity impacts 17% of the European Union's territory and 11% of its population, demonstrating that this is no longer an issue exclusive to the southern European countries (IPCC, 2014; UNESCO, 2009). Therefore, increased urbanization, population growth, economy (agriculture, industry, tourism, renewable energy) growth, stress on catchment areas, expanding regions of water scarcity, and the impacts of climate change on water availability are putting a greater strain on existing drinking water resources. This intensifies the need to identify new or alternative sources of supply (WHO, 2017a). Water reuse is an important alternative for most urban water consumption, being already a reality for potable uses in Australia, Namibia, United States of America, Singapore and Israel (Angelakis & Gikas, 2014) and for non-potable uses in many other countries.

In the European Union, the new urban wastewater treatment directive (UWWTD) (EU, 2024; text agreed between the European Commission, Council and Parliament, to be formally approved later this year) is expected to establish [in article 15(1)] that "*Member States shall systematically promote the reuse of treated wastewater from all urban wastewater treatment plants where appropriate, especially in water-stressed areas, and for all appropriate purposes. The potential for the reuse of treated wastewater shall be assessed taking into account the river basin management plans established under the WFD 2000/60/EC and Member States' decisions under article 2, paragraph 2 of Regulation 2020/741. Member States shall ensure that when treated wastewater is reused or is the reuse is planned, it does not endanger the ecological flow in the receiving waters and there is no adverse effect for the environment and human health. Where treated wastewater is reused for agricultural irrigation, it shall comply with the requirements established under Regulation (EU) 2020/741. When strategies on water resilience at Member States level are available, measures on promoting the reuse of treated wastewater and on the actual reuse shall be considered in these strategies.*"

The Regulation (EU) 2020/741 (EU, 2020a) is the first EU regulatory framework that directly addresses water reuse, and applies since June 2023. It focuses on the minimum requirements of reclaimed water for agricultural irrigation since this harmonization at a European level was considered vital to the internal market functioning regarding agricultural products. The regulation does not consider potable reuse. For drinking water, it refers to the water quality requirements intended for human consumption as laid down in DWD 2020 (EU, 2020b). However, following the ISO fit-for-purpose approach (ISO 16075 series) it outlines the requirements for 'Class A' reclaimed water should be of sufficient quality to irrigate crops consumed raw, and where the edible parts are in direct contact with the reclaimed water – these 'Class A' requirements still differ from the minimum requirements of drinking water (e.g., the parametric value of *E. coli* in Class A water is $\leq 10/100$ ml and 0 in drinking water) (Cardoso et al., 2024). Furthermore, the EU regulation introduces key components of water reuse safety, namely, risk assessment and management, the multi-barrier approach, barriers and prevention measures,

monitoring and, for 'Class A', validation campaigns, again following the ISO 20426:2018 and ISO 16075-2:2015 standards. In Portugal, despite several pilot demonstration activities (e.g. conducted by LNEC and AdTA; Viegas et al., 2011, 2015, 2020) and the pioneer legislation on water reuse for all types of non-potable uses (Decree-Law 119/2019 of data), water reuse remains underdeveloped. Although water reuse is included in various local and national water strategies (APA, 2019), it currently accounts for just 1.2% of total volume (ERSAR, 2022), which is far below the national targets of 10% by 2025 and 20% by 2030 (GovPT, 2019).

1.1.2 Lisbon context

Over more than a decade, Lisbon municipality has implemented a climate change mitigation and adaptation strategy, establishing ambitious targets through local plans that align with international commitments such as the Paris Agreement, the Covenant of Mayors, and C40 Cities' Deadline 2020 (C40-ARUP 2016). A key component of the adaptation strategy is a well-established and expanding green infrastructure, structured into nine green corridors, which since 2008 has increased the city's green spaces by 15% without a corresponding rise in water consumption. These corridors ensure an ecological continuum that offers various ecosystem services to residents, including shading to combat the urban heat island effect, water retention and infiltration to mitigate floods, increased urban biodiversity, and enhanced air quality. As a crucial service provider, green infrastructure must be continually improved and expanded, but this should not place additional pressure on drinking water resources (European Commission et al., 2018).

Between 2014 and 2018, Lisbon Municipality achieved a 50% reduction in water consumption, lowering total municipal consumption from about 8 to about 4 million m³ per year, 75% of which (around 3 million m³) was used for non-potable purposes. Using reclaimed water instead of fresh or groundwater when feasible helps to ease the pressure on the city's strategic water reserve (the Castelo de Bode reservoir, located 150 km from Lisbon) and on sensitive groundwater reserves within the city (Cordeiro et al., 2023).

Therefore, in 2019, Lisbon Municipality presented the Strategic Plan for Water Reuse in Lisbon, the result of a close collaboration with the wastewater utility Águas do Tejo Atlântico (AdTA). Framed by a larger policy scope to increase circularity in all areas of urban management, a new water network is being implemented to distribute high-quality reclaimed water from AdTA's Water Resource Recovery Facilities to locations of important non-potable municipal uses, such as irrigation and street washing. Reclaimed water is a sustainable water source, largely unaffected by climate uncertainty, which can contribute to reducing pressure on strategic drinking water resources and tackle the frequent droughts in Portugal and in the Lisbon area (Viegas et al., 2011, 2015, 2020). Lisbon was the first city in Portugal to apply for a permit to use reclaimed water for unrestricted urban irrigation and the licensing of this demanding reuse of very high-quality water was a time-consuming process.

1.1.3 B-WaterSmart context and water reuse in beer production

To encourage the adoption of urban water reuse in Lisbon and its replication in other national and international cities, generating and sharing knowledge is crucial. One of the most significant initiatives supporting this effort is Lisbon's role as one of the six Living Labs (LLs) (six European coastal cities and regions) in the B-WaterSmart H2020 project. B-WaterSmart project aims to accelerate the transformation of Europe's coastal economies and societies into smart water management, with new market models, circularity promotion and data management solutions for multiple sectors and users. Methodologies, tools, and processes were developed to enable the safe use of alternative sources of water, particularly reclaimed water, improve water efficiency and the water-energy nexus, to make cities more resilient to water scarcity and climate change.

Lisbon LL aimed at developing and testing a number of methodologies and tools, namely (a) the Urban Water Cycle Observatory, (b) a suite of methodologies and digital tools to address risk assessment

and management for water reuse and smart (fit-for-purpose) water allocation, (c) a methodology and a digital tool to implement building standards through Climate-Ready Certificates assessing water and energy efficiency in individual apartments, buildings and neighbourhoods, and (d) innovative business models for the water sector, namely associated with water reuse, as well as (e) a protocol for potable water reuse for craft beer production, the subject of the present document.

In the scope of B-WaterSmart project the main goals of this potable reuse study were (i) to prepare the water sector for the anticipated intensification of water scarcity (Oliveira, 2021) and (ii), on the short-term, to help build confidence on safe water reuse.

Having this in mind, the water reuse for beer production was selected as the potable reuse case study. On the one hand, people usually enjoy beer (is a positive memory). Actually, previously to B-WaterSmart project, Águas do Tejo Atlântico developed an awareness campaign related with water reuse in which a craft beer was produced, with local brewers, from advanced treated wastewater. The beer name is VIRA (meaning TURN) with the double meaning of turning (waste)water into enjoyable drinkable water and turning/changing mindsets – ‘water quality matters not its past history’. 15,000 litres of VIRA beer were produced and are served in events promoted by AdTA.

On the other hand, deionised and dechlorinated water is advantageous for beer and soft-drink production and the beer production provides itself a set of downstream additional barriers towards the finished water quality. The craft beer production includes the processes of mashing, boiling, cooling, fermenting and maturing, and bottling. In the mashing process the malt is previously milled with water (in this case the reclaimed potable water) at controlled operational conditions (time, temperature, pH) allowing starch conversion into sugar. Then, at boiling process, the hop is added to the mash and is boiled to gain flavour and aroma. Subsequently, the mixture is cooled. The next step is fermentation, where the yeast is added to transform the sugars into alcohol and carbon dioxide. The final process of bottling involves pasteurization.

1.2 Indirect and direct potable reuse

Potable reuse refers to the use of properly treated wastewater for drinking purposes. As such, it relies on producing safe drinking water from wastewater. Due to the quality of treated wastewater concerning microbial and chemical contamination, potable reuse is often a complex activity generally involving advanced treatment processes and substantial management expertise (WHO, 2017a). Potable reuse can be divided into two different types: direct potable reuse (DPR) and indirect potable reuse (IPR). Direct potable reuse involves introducing highly treated wastewater directly into an existing water supply system. Indirect potable reuse, on the other hand, involves discharging treated wastewater into an environmental buffer, such as a groundwater aquifer or surface water reservoir, before it eventually enters a water supply system (Tchobanoglous et al., 2015).

Both DPR and IPR generally involve advanced treatment of wastewater to produce drinking water. The major difference between DPR and IPR is the use of environmental buffers in IPR. The claimed benefits of environmental buffers vary and include provision of a diluting step, blending, additional contaminant attenuation processes, time to respond to treatment failure and reduction of negative public perceptions (ATSE, 2013).

The advantages of DPR include avoiding potential contamination of treated wastewater in environmental buffers, particularly those involving surface water. Direct potable reuse avoids issues over water access rights, reducing pumping and transport costs and can be applied in locations where suitable environmental buffers are not available (Leverenz et al., 2011; ATSE, 2013). However, a perceived disadvantage of DPR compared with IPR is that the lack of an environmental barrier reduces the time available to respond to treatment failures and other incidents that could impair drinking water quality prior to supply to consumers.

Worldwide, there are several examples of potable reuse, mostly of IPR, while a large number of DPR

installations are still under study, approval or being built, thus with less cases operational (USEPA, 2017; Jeffrey et al., 2022). Globally, potable reuse installations are predominantly US based with additionally multiple installations established in Australia, Singapore and Southern Africa (Namibia and South Africa). For the more numerous IPR plants, the regions most concentrated in large installations are Southern California, which has its first installation operating since 1962, Singapore and Australia (Lazarova et al., 2013; Jeffrey et al., 2022). In Europe, at least two IPR installations exist, in Belgium (Lazarova et al., 2013), which is in operation since 2002, and in Spain (Munné et al., 2023). Regarding DPR, the oldest installation is in Namibia, the Goreangab water reclamation plant in Windhoek, which has been in operation since 1969 (Lazarova et al., 2013; Jeffrey et al., 2022). Other few installations can be found in the USA, South Africa and Sweden, which, according to Jeffrey et al. (2022), is the only DPR installation in Europe.

For craft beer production, besides small pilot projects around the world, the most prominent project is from the Pure Water Brewing Alliance, a pioneering group of utilities, consultants, professional associations, and craft brewers, which have been involved in brewing beer with reclaimed water since 2017 (<https://www.purewaterbrew.org/>).

Public health protection requires that microbiological and chemical constituents in wastewater be removed to the extent practical before discharge to the environment or for other uses. Complete removal of all microorganisms and chemicals is impossible; therefore, goals are established to limit human exposure of specific identified agents to concentrations that are not harmful to human health. The maximum allowable concentrations of these agents are established as standards. In the United States, these standards for drinking water are known as maximum contaminant levels for chemicals and log reduction values (LRVs) for pathogens and faecal indicator bacteria (Tchobanoglous et al., 2015), whereas in the European DWD parametric values are established (EU, 2020b), which member states must implement through their national legislation. Currently, as introduced in Section 1.1.1, there are no regulations specifically setting water quality criteria for direct potable reuse in the European Union. While no such regulations exist, an appropriate approach is to use legislated drinking water quality parameters, as addressed in Chapter 2.

1.3 Scope, objectives and document structure

Potable reuse can represent a realistic and practical source of drinking water in many circumstances and pilot demonstration projects pave the way to future guidelines and best practices. The work developed, within task 2.4.1 of the B-WaterSmart project, aimed at contributing with pilot field data to the development of such guidelines on water quality and reclamation schemes' operation & redundancy for safe production of drinking water from municipal wastewater for craft beer production – during which the reclaimed water is further processed, i.e. a DPR application with downstream additional safety barriers. The goal is to anticipate DPR as a solution for aggravated water scarcity, localised needs, emergency situations, as well as to build the trust of the society in water reuse safety.

The focus of this document is therefore to:

- provide a discussion of the guidance needed for each of the three key components (regulatory, technical, and public outreach) that make up a direct potable reuse for craft beer production;
- analyse different multi-barrier approach schemes to minimize hazards on direct potable reuse for craft beer production and their critical control parameters and points;
- analyse the results obtained during the pilot unit demonstration at Beirolas Water Resource Recovery Facility (WRRF) within the B-WaterSmart Lisbon LL activities;
- define and explain the more reliable potable reuse scheme for craft beer production demonstrated at pilot scale at Beirolas WRRF.

This document is organized into the following chapters:

1. Introduction
2. Regulation and health-based targets
3. Critical parameters and control points
4. Monitoring: field results and recommendations
5. Management and communication
6. Conclusions

An overview of water reuse and direct potable reuse as well as the challenges addressed are presented in Chapter 1. It is intended to serve as a general introduction to potable reuse and to the work developed within B-WaterSmart in the Lisbon LL. In Chapter 2, regulatory issues are addressed and the water quality targets that serve as guidance are presented. The system description, which includes the Beirolas WRRF and the pilot unit developed and tested are described in Chapter 3. Also, in this chapter the multi-barrier approach and the different potable reuse schemes and the corresponding critical control points are analysed. The monitoring program, the identification of sampling points and the main results obtained during the demonstration are addressed in Chapter 4, from which conclusions and recommendations are drawn. In this chapter the more reliable potable reuse scheme for beer production is analysed and explained. Public outreach and communication strategy is addressed in Chapter 5. The main conclusions of this study are presented in Chapter 6. ANNEX I presents the summary of all analytical results (chemical and microbiological).

This document is the result of a collaborative work between Águas do Tejo Atlântico, S.A. (AdTA) and the Laboratório Nacional de Engenharia Civil (LNEC).

2 Regulation and health-based targets

2.1 Applicable or related regulations

At the international level, legislation and regulations for direct potable reuse (DPR) vary significantly. While there is no universally applicable framework governing DPR, several countries and regions have developed their own sets of regulations or guidelines to address this practice.

For example, in the United States, the Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA) provides guidelines and recommendations for Direct Potable Reuse (DPR) through its Water Reuse Action Plan (USEPA, 2019). Additionally, the Framework for Direct Potable Reuse (WaterReuse Research Foundation, 2015) offers further guidance for implementing DPR projects while ensuring public health protection.

Additionally, international organizations such as the World Health Organization (WHO) play crucial roles in developing guidelines and best practices for water reuse, including DPR (WHO, 2017a). These guidelines often serve as references for countries developing their own regulations, e.g. Singapore and Namibia.

Overall, while there is growing interest in DPR as a sustainable water management strategy, the regulatory landscape at the international level remains diverse and evolving, with countries and regions adapting regulations to their specific contexts and priorities.

In Portugal, potable water reuse is not considered nor regulated. For the development of this work, the parameters and target values foreseen on the drinking water quality Portuguese regulation (Decree-Law 69/2023, 21st august), which transposes the European Union's DWD 2020 were used. For other parameters, namely for non-regulated contaminants of emerging concern, the “Guidelines for Drinking-Water Quality” from the World Health Organization (WHO, 2022) and the “Examining the criteria for direct potable reuse” of NWRI-WRRF (2013) were used.

2.2 Water quality targets

The water quality targets are specified in Table 2.1 and Table 2.2.

Table 2.1 – Microbiological targets, parameters and indicators based on DWD 2020.

Parameter	Unit	Parametric value
Microbiological parameters		
Intestinal enterococci	number/100 ml	0
<i>Escherichia coli (E. coli)</i>	number /100 ml	0
Microbiological Indicator parameters		
<i>Clostridium perfringens</i>	number/100 ml	0
Colony count 22° C	number/ml	No change
Coliform bacteria	number/100 ml	0
Somatic coliphages	number/100 ml	50

Table 2.2 – Chemical targets, parameters and indicators based on DWD 2020.

Parameter	Unit	Parametric value
Chemical parameters		
Acrylamide	µg/l	0.1
Antimony	µg/l	10
Arsenic	µg/l	10
Benzene	µg/l	1
Benzo(a)pyrene	µg/l	0.01
Bisphenol A	µg/l	2.5
Boron	mg/l	1.5
Bromate	µg/l	10
Cadmium	µg/l	5
Chlorate	mg/l	0.25
Chlorite	mg/l	0.25
Chromium	µg/l	25
Copper	mg/l	2
Cyanide	µg/l	50
1,2-dichloroethane	µg/l	3
Epichlorohydrin	µg/l	0.1
Fluoride	mg/l	1.5
Haloacetic acids (HAAs)	µg/l	60
Lead	µg/l	5
Mercury	µg/l	1
Microcystin-LR	µg/l	1
Nickel	µg/l	20
Nitrate	mg/l	50
Nitrite	mg/l	0.5
Pesticides	µg/l	0.1
Pesticides total	µg/l	0.5
PFAS total	µg/l	0.5
Sum of PFAS	µg/l	0.1
Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons	µg/l	0.1
Selenium	µg/l	20
Tetrachloroethene and Trichloroethene	µg/l	10
Trihalomethanes total	µg/l	100
Uranium a-,b-total	µg/l	30
Vinyl chloride	µg/l	0.5

Parameter	Unit	Parametric value
Chemical Indicator parameters		
Aluminium	µg/l	200
Ammonium	mg/l	0.5
Chloride	mg/l	250
Conductivity	µS.cm ⁻¹	2500
pH	-	≥ 6.5 ≤ 9.5
Iron	µg/l	200
Manganese	µg/l	50
Oxidisability	mg/l	5
Sulphate	mg/l	250
Sodium	mg/l	200
Total Organic Carbon (TOC)		No change
Turbidity	NTU	1

3 Critical parameters and control points

3.1 System description

3.1.1 Beirolas WRRF

The pilot unit was installed at the Beirolas Water Resource Recovery Facility (WRRF) which has been in operation since 1989. It serves the municipalities of Lisbon and Loures and discharges treated effluent into Tagus River Estuary. The facility serves a population equivalent of 213,540 inhabitants, with an average daily flow rate of 54,500 m³/d, and it has the capability to treat a peak flow rate of 3,000 m³/h, during dry weather and a peak flow rate of 4,600 m³/h in wet weather conditions. The wastewater is predominantly domestic, with a relatively minor industrial contribution. During high tide levels in the estuary, salt intrusion occurs in the sewage network, reaching the WRRF.

Figure 3.1 – View of Beirolas WRRF (left, Source: Águas do Tejo Atlântico), Map location of Beirolas WRRF (right).

The wastewater treatment process begins with pre-treatment, which includes coarse solids screening, sand removal and degreasing. Subsequently, it progresses to primary treatment with primary sedimentation clarifiers and after to an equalization tank. The secondary treatment includes an anaerobic/anoxic/oxic (A2O) activated sludge system for biological treatment, followed by secondary clarifiers. Afterwards, the wastewater undergoes filtration through sand filters before being discharged into the Tagus River. The quality requirements of discharge permit are shown in Table 3.1.

In addition, the WRRF features two water reuse treatment lines for irrigation, street cleaning and internal reuse (Figure 3.2). The one designed for internal uses includes 50 µm microfilters, UV disinfection and sodium hypochlorite dosing. The recycled water must meet Class B requirements outlined in the Portuguese Decree-Law No. 119/2019, of August 21 (DL 119/2019; Table 3.1).

The other reuse treatment line is dedicated to external uses, such as public greenspaces irrigation within the Lisbon Municipality. This line is also equipped with 50 µm microfilters, an ultrafiltration (UF) system with a membrane porosity of 0.04 µm with 20 membrane modules, and sodium hypochlorite dosing (Figure 3.2). The UF system has the capacity to treat 1,200 m³/d. The recycled water must meet Class A requirements outlined in the Portuguese DL 119/2019 (Table 3.1).

Figure 3.2 – Beirolas WRRF water reuse treatment lines (Source: Águas do Tejo Atlântico).

Table 3.1 – Quality requirements for Beirolas WRRF effluent and reclaimed water for internal and external uses (Source: Portuguese Decree-Law No. 152/97 and Decree-Law No. 119/2019).

Parameter	Unit	Beirolas WRRF effluent	Reclaimed water internal uses Class B	Reclaimed water external uses Class A
COD	mg O ₂ /l	≤ 125	-	-
BOD ₅	mg O ₂ /l	≤ 25	≤ 25	≤ 10
TSS	mg/l	≤ 35	≤ 35	≤ 10
<i>E. coli</i>	CFU/100 ml	-	≤ 100	≤ 10
Turbidity	NTU	-	-	≤ 5

The pilot treatment line could be fed with these three diverse sources of water (Beirolas WRRF effluent, reclaimed water Class B and reclaimed water Class A). However, during the project demonstration, only the effluent from the Beirolas WRRF and the reclaimed water for external uses – Class A were used. The average quality of these sources during 2023 is detailed in Table 3.2.

Table 3.2 – Average quality of Beirolas WRRF effluent and of reclaimed water for external uses - Class A, during 2023 (Source: Águas do Tejo Atlântico).

Parameter	Unit	Beirolas WRRF effluent	Reclaimed water external uses Class A
COD	mg O ₂ /l	37.6	N/A
BOD ₅	mg O ₂ /l	6.0	< 6.0

Parameter	Unit	Beirolas WRRF effluent	Reclaimed water external uses Class A
TSS	mg/l	4.4	< 3
TN	mg N/l	13.0	11.9
Ammonium	mg NH ₄ /l	3.8	2.3
Nitrates	mg N/l	7.9	6.9
TP	mg P/l	4.0	3.4
<i>E. coli</i>	CFU/100 ml	3 x 10 ³	0
Turbidity	NTU	-	< 0.1

3.1.2 Pilot unit

The pilot unit was installed on a container designed with a sustainability focus. It features an outer cork coating and incorporates a photovoltaic panel system for energy self-consumption (Figure 3.3).

The potable reuse pilot comprised four advanced treatment technologies: ozonation (O₃), biologically active granular activated carbon (BAC) filtration, and a 3-stage reverse osmosis (RO) system.

The pilot unit had a production capacity of 1,250 L/h and was designed for a continuous and automated treatment process, allowing remote monitoring of several operational parameters. The combination of the treatment processes can be switched. A simplified diagram is provided in Figure 3.4.

This pilot unit was an upgrade from what was foreseen in the grant agreement in the best interest of the project, from a batch ozone-RO pilot planned, first, to a continuous 24/7 pilot with automation and online monitoring, which enables to improve the reliability and stability of the process and safety/quality of the water produced, and, second, to include an activated carbon filter column for a better control of biofouling of the RO.

Figure 3.3 – Pilot unit installed at Beirolas WRRF and group photo during the NTNU visit in November 2022.

Figure 3.4 – Pilot unit system diagram.

The ozonation system was equipped with a WEDECO EFFIZON GSO 10/20 ozone generator, capable of converting oxygen (liquid oxygen provided by Nippon gases, at a minimum of 99.5%) into ozone with a production capacity of 30 g O₃/h, an ozonation contact chamber that includes a high-pressure pump and a hydro-injector for ozone dissolution, and a Venturi injector that achieves an ozone transfer efficiency of over 90%.

This system was designed to provide a variable ozone dose (5 to 10 mg O₃/L were tested, corresponding to 1-2 mg O₃/mg TOC), with a contact time of approximately 45 minutes. The chamber was fed with 1.7-1.8 m³/h of water. A turbidimeter was installed at the inlet of the ozone chamber and a redox potential probe after the chamber. At this stage, sodium bisulfite (NaHSO₃, 38.5%) could be dosed for neutralizing oxidizing agents (ozone or free chlorine residuals) that otherwise could damage the membranes.

Following the ozone chamber, a feed tank was placed to maintain a consistent feed to the reverse osmosis (RO) system. It was designed for a contact time ranging from 84 to 98 minutes, allowing for the decay of residual ozone in the treated water, taking into account the limitations associated with reverse osmosis membranes in handling feedwater containing oxidizing agents.

During the demonstration, a granular activated carbon (GAC) column filter featuring an activated carbon with an 8 x 30 mesh, WT 830 from Media Carb, Switzerland, was installed. This activated carbon was derived from bituminous coal and steam activated. The prolonged operation of the GAC as well as its combination with ozone fosters the biological properties of the GAC, thus converting it into a biologically active carbon (BAC) filtration system.

The bed volume of the BAC system was approximately 137 L, providing an empty bed contact time (EBCT) of around 5 minutes. Throughout the demonstration, the system was in operation for 31 thousand bed volumes (kBV), which translates to approximately 3.5 months of continuous operation.

After the BAC filter, there was a set of two parallel microfilter cartridges (Wasser) made of melt-down polypropylene fibres to protect the RO system, including from the GAC filter fines. The RO system had a 3-stage configuration with a 2:1:1 vessel arrangement with recirculation. Each vessel comprised 2 RO membranes, Hydranautics CPA5-LD-4040, made of polyamide composite offering high salt rejection, exceeding 99.5% for NaCl. The system included eight membrane modules with a total membrane area of approximately 60 m². The water recovery rates (WRR) for this system were set at 70% or 60%, depending on the operational performance. The RO operated automatically to produce a constant permeate flow rate of 1,250 L/h (at 70% WRR) or 1,000 L/h (at 60 % WRR).

For scaling prevention, an antiscalant was dosed (Genesys LF, 3 mg/l) at the inlet of the microfilters, and acid dosing was also an option. For biofouling control, sodium hypochlorite (13 %, as received, further diluted to 1.95 %) was occasionally (in some trials) dosed to the RO feed tank, with a set-point of 0.9 mg Cl₂/L. Chlorine was monitored for free chlorine and total chlorine, by the DPD method (APHA-AWWA-WEF, 1998), at the pilot inlet and at the membranes' inlet. Additionally, clean-in-place (CIP) was conducted regularly for cleaning and maintenance, helping to ensure the longevity and optimal performance of the system. Depending on the foulants, alkaline CIP (Auxiclean B-13, at a pH ≤ 13) or acid CIP (Auxiclean A – 1.6, at a pH ≥ 1) were performed, according to the membrane's specification.

3.2 Hazards

3.2.1 General principles

The water produced by potable reuse schemes can include numerous hazards that can compromise the use of water for direct potable reuse, but not all will represent significant risks to human health (WHO, 2017a). The same can be applied to the potable reuse schemes for craft beer production. To manage the higher concentrations of microbial pathogens and wide array of potential chemical contaminants, potable reuse schemes typically incorporate complex combinations of control measures, including industrial discharge management, water and wastewater treatment processes, and the use of natural systems to provide high levels of pathogen removal and protection against chemical hazards (WHO, 2017a).

From a risk management perspective, the removal and disinfection of pathogens remain the most critical issues in the design of potable reuse schemes since acute exposures can lead to immediate disease outbreak. Chemical contaminants with limited exceptions (e.g. copper and nitrate) are generally not considered acute threats but long-term chronic exposures may lead to adverse health outcomes (WHO, 2017a).

3.2.2 Microbiological hazards

Unsafe drinking water can be a significant source of enteric pathogens with the potential to cause large outbreaks (MacKenzie et al., 1994; Hruday & Hruday, 2004a, 2014b); hence, protecting public health from waterborne illness caused by microbial hazards is of paramount importance (WHO, 2017a).

The wastewater drainage system collects wastewater that contains pathogens, diverse in characteristics and behaviour, which include bacteria, viruses, protozoa and helminths. Nevertheless,

the greatest risk from exposure to wastewater is gastrointestinal disease following ingestion of enteric pathogens (WHO, 2017a).

3.2.3 Chemical hazards

Wastewater also contains various chemical hazards originating from human activities, encompassing industrial chemicals, substances excreted by humans, as well as those used in household activities, personal care and pharmaceuticals. Metals and inorganic chemicals are generally present in higher concentrations (μg to mg per L) while pharmaceuticals and personal care products, when detected, are generally present in lower concentrations (ng to μg per L) (WHO, 2017a). Different studies indicate the chemicals existing on wastewater can be broad, but concentrations typically detected are well below those that would represent a risk to public health (Schwab et al., 2005; NRMCC-EPHC-NHMRC, 2006-2009; Snyder et al., 2008; Bruce et al., 2010; Bull et al., 2011; WHO, 2012).

Potential chemical hazards identified include contaminants of emerging concern (CECs), namely trace organic compounds including per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) and alkylphenols. PFAS are persistent and some are highly water soluble. They are used in the production of water-resistant and stain-resistant products, including furniture fabrics, cookware and clothing, as well as in firefighting foams.

Another issue related with potable reuse schemes is the disinfection byproducts that are formed by reactions between disinfectants and organic and inorganic constituents of water. According to WHO (2017a), high initial concentrations of organic components, ammonia, bromide or iodide in wastewater may lead to elevated production of various, and sometimes unique, disinfection byproducts, such as bromate, chlorate, trihalomethanes (THMs), haloacetic acids (HAAs) and N-nitrosodimethylamine (NDMA).

3.3 Hazards control

3.3.1 General principles

As described in Section 3.2, there are different hazards and therefore specific control measures have to be defined to guarantee the water quality for direct potable reuse in craft beer production.

According to WHO (2017a), control measures should be applied from drainage system to the end of the potable reuse scheme. For example, source control measures designed to prevent contamination as close to the source as possible (e.g. industrial waste controls) are essential and should be included. For this specific protocol and because it is a demonstration in the scope of the innovation project B-WaterSmart, the control measures implemented and studied comprised the potable reuse schemes applied at pilot-scale. The treatment technologies selected and studied in this demonstration project were technologies that are commonly used in advanced treatment to reduce concentrations of remaining microbial and chemical hazards to acceptable levels.

The control measures were defined and studied for the advanced treatment according to a multi-barrier approach. The multi-barrier approach ensures that performance failure at a single barrier should not lead to significant failure to remove microbial or chemical contaminants (WHO, 2017a). The same can be applied for potable reuse schemes for direct potable reuse for craft beer production, which was the scope of this project.

The selection of potable reuse schemes should also take into consideration the level of reliability that can be achieved through the concepts of redundancy, robustness and resilience (Pecson et al., 2015), considering reliability as “a measurement of the ability of a component or system to perform its designated function without failure” (USEPA, 1974), with which the ISO 20468-1:2018 agrees. It is also important to note that the reliability concept applies not only to the system, but also to individual system components. According to WHO (2017a) for potable reuse schemes, reliability is used to

describe the ability of the system to provide water that consistently meets the public health protection.

3.3.2 Control measures / multi-barrier approach / treatment schemes tested

Multiple barrier systems are a component of potable reuse schemes as they provide several individual processes capable of stopping the flow of pathogenic organisms and chemical substances into treated effluent water (USEPA, 2017). The purpose of multiple barriers is to decrease the probability of process failure by adding units of reliability and redundancy to the treatment scheme; this ensures that if one step of the process fails, another treatment unit will reliably provide public health protection (ATSE, 2013).

According to WHO (2017a) report on potable reuse, it is recommended that multi-barrier treatment designs should ensure that each pollutant should be reduced in concentration by at least two, and preferably by three or more, processes. More recently, the State Water Resources Control Board of California (USA) in its regulations for direct potable reuse, is requiring, for pathogen and chemicals control, that the treatment train shall consist of no less than three diverse treatment mechanisms, including physical separation and inactivation (SWRCB, 2024).

In line with these recommendations, and although in the present work the reclaimed water is intended for beer production, which is a DPR application with downstream additional safety barriers, the pilot unit was specifically designed to include additional multiple barriers in addition to the conventional treatment of WRRF. Mainly to address:

- suspended solids (UF, BAC and RO, besides the full-scale sand and 50- μm filters);
- microbiological contaminants (UF, ozonation, chlorination and RO);
- dissolved chemicals and trace organic compounds (ozonation, BAC and RO).

The diagram in Figure 3.5 illustrates the four advanced potable reuse schemes that were tested and demonstrated at Beirolas WRRF, in the scope of B-WaterSmart project, to produce water for craft beer production. These type of control measures were studied to benchmark them towards hazards control and to identify the most reliable potable reuse scheme, also considering the quality of feed water.

Scheme 1

This potable reuse scheme included three treatment barriers: UF, ozonation (O_3) and RO. The pilot included an UF unit, an ozonation chamber, a feed tank, 5 μm microfilters, and a 3-stage RO system. In this scheme, the RO system was operated with a WRR of 70%, yielding a permeate flowrate of 1.25 m^3/h .

Scheme 2

This potable reuse scheme included three treatment barriers: UF, chlorination (Cl_2) and RO. Downstream the UF unit, chlorine (Cl_2) was dosed in low concentrations (0.9 mg/L) to prevent biofouling and no ozonation was included before the final RO step. In this scheme, the RO system was operated with a WRR of 70%, yielding a permeate flowrate of 1.25 m^3/h and with a WRR of 60%, producing a permeate flowrate of 1 m^3/h .

Scheme 3

This potable reuse scheme included five treatment barriers: UF, chlorination, ozonation, BAC and RO. Chlorine was dosed (at 0.9 mg/L) after the UF treatment step, and a BAC filter was installed between ozonation and RO stages.

Scheme 4

This potable reuse scheme included three treatment barriers: ozonation, BAC and RO, described above.

Figure 3.5 – Potable reuse schemes tested and demonstrated in the pilot unit at Beirolas WRRF.

3.3.3 Validation of control measures

Control measures used in potable reuse schemes, which could be adopted to the craft beer production, need to be validated to demonstrate that individual processes will meet performance targets and reliability to produce safe water and ensure that public health is protected (WHO, 2017a). Validation is the process of obtaining evidence that selected control measures will be effective in achieving specified levels of hazard reduction. It also defines the operational criteria required to ensure that the control measures continue to function effectively (Bartram et al., 2009). Validation can take three basic forms (WHO, 2017a):

- evaluation of existing data and information, such as published data and manufacturer-conducted challenge studies;
- evaluation of results from process-specific certification schemes;
- on-site testing of pilot-scale processes or full-scale systems.

The approach herein followed includes two of the validation forms specified above.

Evaluation of existing data and information, such as published data and manufacturer-conducted challenge studies – the following complementary activities were conducted:

- a) a brief critical review of the technologies and specific studies for direct potable reuse was performed. This activity supported the selection of the potable reuse schemes and technologies that were applied for pilot-scale demonstration at Beirolas WRRF;
- b) analysis of the results from previous AdTA's experiences, in which safe water for craft beer production was produced in batch mode;

- c) analysis of the results and lessons learnt in TRUST and LIFE Impetus projects, in which membrane 24/7 pilots were operated (ceramic microfiltration; Viegas et al., 2025, 2020) and intensive monitoring campaigns of emerging contaminants were conducted at Beirolas WRRF, respectively, both key aspects of the topic and the field work addressed.

On-site testing of pilot-scale processes – the following complementary activities were conducted:

- a) a pilot unit with the system described in Section 3.1 was developed and four different potable reuse schemes were defined for testing and demonstrating different multi-barrier approaches and control measures;
- b) an extensive monitoring campaign of water quality for the potable reuse schemes (once per treatment train) and regular monitoring campaigns (once a week) were defined for validating the intermediate barriers;
- c) the operational criteria that can be used to demonstrate ongoing performance of control measures were identified. The operational monitoring parameters are required to ensure that any deviation from required performance is detected in due time (WHO, 2017a);
- d) the system integrity monitoring was designed, including online UF and RO flowrate, pressure and turbidity, and RO pH and electrical conductivity;
- e) three critical control points (CCPs) and the associated critical parameters to be monitored were established for the potable reuse schemes as illustrated in Figure 3.6:
 - turbidity at the UF outlet;
 - ORP at the ozonation outlet (or the status of the ozone generator); and
 - conductivity at the RO outlet;

For each monitoring parameter and based on existing studies, an alarm value was established in the unit's automatic control system to inform the pilot unit's operation team whenever a barrier is (likely to be) operating incorrectly. The operation team was then to decide whether to carry out maintenance or cleaning tasks of the system, and potentially stop it if needed;

- f) the sampling points for water quality control were established (explained in more detail in Section 4.1). A plan for calibration and verification of online measurements was developed - where online monitoring is performed, results are to be regularly verified and calibrated, if needed, using grab samples and bench top analyses.

Figure 3.6 – Critical control points in the potable reuse schemes.

4 Monitoring: field results and recommendations

According to WHO (2017a), a comprehensive monitoring and control system is necessary to measure and track the performance of potable reuse schemes, to ensure that operational targets are being met. Monitoring needs to be undertaken at a frequency that will enable rapid and timely responses if significant deviations occur that could affect water quality. Tiered operational monitoring programs that emphasize expedite methods or online measures with real-time data reporting are critical so that anomalies can be rapidly detected, and measures can be accordingly taken on time (WHO, 2017a).

The monitoring activities took place during the pilot demonstrations, spanning from April 2023 to March 2024. During this period, more than 200 microbiological analyses and 4000 chemical analyses, including of emerging contaminants and of DBPs, were performed.

4.1 Water quality monitoring in the pilot study

4.1.1 Sampling points

Verification of water quality provides a final check on the suitability of the water produced from potable reuse schemes for craft beer production with adequate quality for health protection. In Figure 4.1 the different sampling points for water quality monitoring are identified. Their verification provides an assessment of the effectiveness of the pilot system in achieving compliance with health-based targets.

According to WHO (2017a), verification of water quality should typically include testing for faecal indicator organisms and hazardous chemicals with regulatory limits. In this specific project and demonstration, as discussed in Chapter 2, there is no regulatory framework for direct potable reuse. Therefore, for the verification of these parameters the values and parameters of the DWD 2020 (EU, 2020b) were used. Also, for this work and to develop a reclamation protocol for water reuse in craft beer production, quality assurance and quality control programs were essential, including the use of standardized methods and certified/accredited laboratories wherever possible. This is vital to ensure confidence in results and to enable proper interpretation of results.

Figure 4.1 – Water quality monitoring sampling points.

4.1.2 Microbiological parameters

Monitoring microbial pathogens in water produced by potable reuse schemes is impractical and often of little value (WHO, 2017a). The traditional approach to verifying microbial quality is the use of faecal indicators such as *E. coli* and this approach was used in this pilot demonstration. A limitation of *E. coli* is that it is not a particularly good indicator of enteric viruses and protozoa, which are more resistant to environmental pressures. As such, other indicators were defined, namely somatic coliphages and F-specific RNA bacteriophages (for enteric viruses), *Clostridium* spp. (for protozoa and enterococci), and *Clostridium perfringens* (for enteric bacteria), with some of these parameters also foreseen in the DWD 2020 with parametric values. Since RO is a physical barrier against bacteria and genes by size-exclusion, the selected microbial indicators are also surrogates of microbial parameters of emerging concern, e.g. antibiotic-resistant bacteria and antibiotic-resistance genes, which were then not monitored. The monitoring plan for microbiological water quality includes the parameters listed in Table 4.1 for the sampling points identified in Figure 4.2, where applicable, depending on the scheme in operation.

Table 4.1 – Microbiological parameters included in the monitoring plan.

Monitoring type / frequency	Parameter
Regular analytical monitoring once a week	<i>E. coli</i>
Extended analytical monitoring for each scheme	F-specific bacteriophages, somatic coliphages
	<i>Clostridium perfringens</i> spores / spore-forming sulphate-reducing bacteria
	Intestinal enterococci *
	Colony count 22° C *
	Coliform bacteria *

* The identified parameters were only analysed at the sampling point BEI-PT-RO12, which is the final potable water for craft beer production.

4.1.3 Chemical parameters

Since no regulation exists for direct potable reuse in Portugal or in the EU, all the chemical parameters included in the DWD 2020 were monitored. To increase the confidence by operators and consumers in the safety of water produced by potable reuse schemes, other disinfection byproducts and a wide range of contaminants of emerging concern were also monitored.

The monitoring plan for chemical water quality includes the parameters listed in Table 4.2 for the sampling points identified in Figure 4.2, where applicable, depending on the scheme in operation.

Table 4.2 – Chemical parameters included in the monitoring plan.

Monitoring type / frequency	Parameter
Regular analytical monitoring once a week	Conductivity
	Turbidity and ORP
	Organic matter parameters (TOC/DOC, A254, A436, SUVA)
	NH ₄ , NO ₃ , KN, TN, TP
	Hardness
	Alkalinity
Extended analytical monitoring for each scheme	54 Pharmaceutical compounds
	Estrogenic hormones: 17-β-estradiol and 17-α-ethinylestradiol
	Bisphenol A
	Alkylphenols
	20 PFAS (PFOS, PFOA, PFOSA)
	Toxicity (<i>Daphnia magna</i> + <i>Vibrio fischeri</i>)
	Bromide, Bromate
	NDMA
	THMs
	HAAs
	Drinking Water Directive 2020 parameters *

* The identified parameters were only analysed at the sampling point BEI-PT-RO12, which is the final potable water for craft beer production.

4.2 Operational monitoring in the pilot study

According to WHO (2017a), having monitoring data available to prevent and correct deterioration of the performance of each unit barrier in a potable reuse scheme is the key for assuring consistent production of safe water, in this case, for craft beer production. Monitoring of unit processes at control points within a treatment train requires identification of appropriate parameters and target criteria to define operational performance acceptability. Target criteria can take the form of operational limits and critical limits. Critical limits for treatment processes used in potable reuse separate acceptable from unacceptable performance and loss of confidence in water safety. Depending on the nature of the control measure, critical limits can be upper limits (e.g. filtered water turbidity), lower limits (e.g. disinfectant Ct values) or ranges of values (e.g. pH).

Operational limits are typically used as early-warning signals that performance of control measures is deteriorating and that corrective actions must be implemented. Considering the above mentioned, the operational monitoring points (Figure 4.2) and the corresponding parameters and target criteria were defined.

Figure 4.2 – Operational monitoring points of the pilot unit (in the green boxes).

According to WHO (2017a), in potable reuse schemes, pathogen control is achieved by a combination of physical removal and inactivation processes. The most widely used operational monitoring parameters are disinfectant residuals and physical removal parameters such as turbidity, both parameters monitored online.

Physical and chemical tests must be conducted, such as the integrity of low-pressure membranes, in this case UF membranes, and can be assessed by online turbidity measurements and periodic pressure decay tests (USEPA, 2005). According to WHO (2017a), integrity of high-pressure membranes, in this case RO membranes, can be monitored by online measurement of conductivity (representing TDS rejection) and TOC. Other parameters such as pH and turbidity are also important and should be regularly monitored for ensuring effective disinfection.

For operational monitoring of chemical compounds, the most suitable approach, according to WHO (2017a), is to measure performance of unit processes through bulk parameters that often can be monitored using online monitoring or high-frequency grab samples and can be used for real-time decision-making for process control. Examples include TOC and conductivity.

Considering the above, for this specific pilot unit the parameters and target criteria were identified (Table 4.3).

Table 4.3 – Operational monitoring points, associated parameters of the pilot unit.

Operational monitoring point	Parameter	Type of measurement	Criteria (acceptable value/range)
BEI-PT-OZ in	Turbidity	Online	-
	Flow rate	Occasional	1.8 m ³ /h (set-point)
BEI-PT-OZ out	ORP	Online	≥ 500 mV, when ozonation is working
BEI-PT-BAC in	Pressure	Online	< 0.5 bar pressure increase (vs. initial pressure)
BEI-PT-RO1	Pressure	Occasional	< 0.5 bar pressure gradient between the microfilters' inlet and outlet
	ORP	Online	< 250 mV
	pH	Online	-
BEI-PT-RO2	Pressure	Online	> 1.5 bar
	Temperature	Online	< 45 °C
	Conductivity	Online	-
BEI-PT-RO3	Pressure	Online	-
BEI-PT-RO4	Pressure	Occasional	-
BEI-PT-RO5	Pressure	Occasional	-
BEI-PT-RO6	Pressure	Online	-
BEI-PT-RO7	Flow rate	Online	0.50 m ³ /h (set-point) - for 70% WRR 0.90 m ³ /h (set-point) - for 60% WRR
BEI-PT-RO8	Flow rate	Online	0.54 m ³ /h (set-point) - for 70% WRR 0.67 m ³ /h (set-point) - for 60% WRR
BEI-PT-RO9	Conductivity	Occasional	-
BEI-PT-RO10	Conductivity	Occasional	-
BEI-PT-RO11	Conductivity	Occasional	-
BEI-PT-RO12	Conductivity	Online	< 50 μS cm ⁻¹
	Turbidity	Online	< 0.1 NTU
	Flow rate	Online	1.25 m ³ /h - for 70% WRR 1.00 m ³ /h - for 60% WRR

A set of performance indicators was additionally computed during the demonstration to diagnose the RO system operation and cleaning needs:

- **Normalized permeate flow** / membrane permeability – permeate flow normalized for temperature and pressure (function of the feedwater temperature, feed and permeate pressures and feedwater TDS); a decrease of more than 10% of normalized permeate flow calls for cleaning.
- **Normalized salt passage** – % permeation of TDS or conductivity (or % rejection decrease); an increase > 10% of Normalized salt passage calls for cleaning.
- **Normalized pressure drop** (ΔP) – difference between the inlet to the first membrane elements and the concentrate stream pressure coming off the tail end elements of each stage or train; Normalized pressure drop increase more than 15% calls for cleaning.

4.3 Monitoring results of the pilot unit

During the demonstration 6,500+ analyses were performed for 200 parameters, 60+ of which of contaminants of emerging concern (as referred throughout Chapter 4). A summary of all analytical results (chemical and microbiological) is presented in ANNEX I – Summary of all analytical results.

4.3.1 Microbiological water quality results

During the pilot demonstration, around 200 microbiological analyses were conducted. None of the microbiological parameters were detected in any of the finished waters for craft beer production across all schemes. Regarding *E. coli*, *Clostridium perfringens* and its spores they were only detected after ozonation in scheme 4, which did not include UF. In this scheme, the ozonation with 2 mg O₃/mg TOC proved ineffective as a complete barrier, although the RO successfully prevented their presence. In the other schemes, the UF process proved to be an effective barrier against these indicators. Additionally, somatic coliphages and F-specific RNA bacteriophages were never detected, neither at the inlet nor at the outlet.

With respect to the treatment process efficiency measured as log-reduction values of microbial indicators, this study was conducted with no spiking, to fully represent the real environment. Therefore, the conducted demonstration of the removal of naturally arising pathogens was limited by their low feedwater concentration. For example, regarding *E. coli*, the UF treated water (schemes 1, 2 and 3, in a total 30 analysis) showed *E. coli* values below the LOQ (1 CFU/100 mL) except during the commissioning phase (scheme 2), when a value of 3 CFU/100 mL was observed. The sand-filtered effluent varied from 3x10³ to 3x10⁵ and thus the LRVs obtained with UF were limited by these intake values, varying between >3.5 and >5.2, values fully aligned with the indicative LRVs compiled in USEPA (2012), i.e., 4 to >6 LRV. When UF was not part of the treatment train (scheme 4) and ozonation was the first barrier, it was observed that an ozone dose of 2 mg O₃/mg DOC was not always fully effective for *E. coli* inactivation, being observed values between 1 (LOQ) and 23 CFU/100 mL after ozonation. The calculated LRVs were between 1.8 and >3.4, also aligned with the indicative LRVs compiled in USEPA (2012), i.e. 2 to 6.

Regarding the other microbial indicators analysed, i.e. *Clostridium perfringens* and its spores and Somatic coliphages, it was observed that UF was fully effective for their removal. Nevertheless, as the sand filtered effluents were not analysed, the UF LRVs could not be assessed. Again, it was observed in scheme 4 that ozonation was not fully effective for inactivating *Clostridium perfringens* and its spores, as expected (USEPA, 2012), being observed values of 800 CFU/100 mL and 520 CFU/50 mL, respectively. Somatic coliphages were not detected in any of the 11 samples analysed.

4.3.2 Chemical water quality results

In the demonstration, a multitude of chemical analyses were conducted (more than 6,000 analyses), yielding a variety of results. A summary of the key findings is herein presented.

Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS)

In Figure 4.3, Figure 4.4, Figure 4.5 and Figure 4.6, the concentrations of detected PFAS throughout each of the schemes are presented, as well as the corresponding removal rates. Across all potable reuse schemes, the concentrations of the individual PFAS and the sum of 20 PFAS in the potable water for craft beer production are below the limit of quantification (LOQ), which are much below the DWD 2020 parametric value of 100 ng/L. The removal rates of each potable reuse scheme and of RO were limited by the LOQ values.

Figure 4.3 – PFAS concentrations throughout scheme 1 and removal rates.

Figure 4.4 – PFAS concentrations throughout scheme 2 and removal rates.

Figure 4.5 – PFAS concentrations throughout scheme 3 and removal rates.

Figure 4.6 – PFAS concentrations throughout scheme 4 and removal rates.

Pharmaceutical compounds (PhCs)

In Figure 4.7, Figure 4.8, Figure 4.9 and Figure 4.10, the concentrations of detected pharmaceutical compounds throughout each of the schemes are presented, as well as the corresponding removal rates. Diclofenac, hydrochlorothiazide, iomeprol and iopromide are the dominant PhCs in the influents to all potable reuse schemes. It can be observed that while the ozonation and the BAC filter contributed to the removal of some PhCs, e.g. diclofenac, gabapentin, iomeprol and hydrochlorothiazide, the overall removal in each scheme was guaranteed by the RO system. Across all potable reuse schemes, the concentrations of all the pharmaceutical compounds in the finished waters for craft beer production are below the corresponding LOQs, which were commonly 100 ng/L, although varying between schemes and parameters. The removal rates of each potable reuse scheme and RO were limited by the LOQ values.

Figure 4.7 – PhC concentrations throughout scheme 1 and removal rates.

Figure 4.8 – PhC concentrations throughout scheme 2 and removal rates.

Figure 4.9 – PhC concentrations throughout scheme 3 and removal rates.

Figure 4.10 – PhC concentrations throughout scheme 4 and removal rates.

Estrogenic hormones and alkylphenols

The estrogenic hormones 17-β-estradiol and 17-α-ethinylestradiol were not detected in any of the schemes. The LOQ was 0.100 µg/L for the first three schemes, while for scheme 4 it was 0.050 µg/L. The same occurred to alkylphenols, that were not detected throughout the demonstration, with LOQs varying from 0.010 µg/L to 0.100 µg/L, depending on the compound.

N-Nitrosodimethylamine (NDMA)

Figure 4.11 shows the concentration of NDMA across the four potable reuse schemes. Despite an increase in NDMA concentration was observed for the schemes using ozonation (negative removal efficiencies in Figure 4.11), all concentration values recorded remained below the thresholds of 100 ng/L and 10 ng/L set for drinking water by WHO (2022) and for potable reuse by NWRI-WRRF (2013) guidelines, respectively. The maximum RO removal rate was around 50%, while for scheme 1 the removal rate was only 29%. This rate was not possible to calculate for scheme 4 due to the samples being damaged during transportation.

Figure 4.11 – NDMA concentration throughout potable reuse schemes and removal rates.

Haloacetic acids (HAAs)

Figure 4.12 shows the concentration of HAAs detected in scheme 2. The 9 HAAs were not detected in scheme 3 and not analysed in scheme 1. In scheme 4, dibromoacetic (DBA), monobromoacetic (MBA) and trichloroacetic (TCA) acids were detected after ozonation with concentrations below 1.7 µg/L but not after the RO. HAAs concentrations in the finished waters from all schemes were below the LOQ, 1 µg/L or 10 µg/L for the sum of 5 HAAs 5 µg/L, which is far below the European DWD 2020 parametric value of 60 ng/L for 5 HAAs, and below the LOQ of 5 µg/L or 50 µg/L for the sum of 9 HAAs.

Figure 4.12 – HAA concentrations throughout scheme 2 and removal rates.

4.3.3 Operational results

During the demonstration, the operational monitoring of the pilot unit included several parameters and indicators. This section presents and discusses some of the results obtained. The RO feed pressure and feed electrical conductivity throughout the demonstration are depicted in Figure 4.13 and Figure 4.14, respectively. These figures illustrate fluctuations in feed pressure, largely attributable to variations in feed electrical conductivity, as peaks in electrical conductivity, due to salt intrusion in the sewage network, reflected in the RO feed pressure.

Figure 4.13 – RO feed pressure during the demonstration.

Figure 4.14 – RO feed electrical conductivity during the demonstration.

The Net Driving Pressure (NDP) is the effective pressure used to permeate the water in the RO system. Figure 4.15 presents the NDP results found during the demonstration. It indicates that scheme 2 had the lowest energy demand to operate. The occurrences of increased pressure were mainly associated with biofouling issues, which were addressed through flushing and CIP (cleaning in place) procedures.

Figure 4.15 – RO net driving pressure during the demonstration.

4.4 Main conclusions from this specific demo

4.4.1 Water quality towards beer production

Regarding the parameters of the DWD 2020, the waters from all schemes analysed were compliant, except for pH. As salts were removed with RO, the pH values were below 6 whereas the parametric range is between 6.5 and 9.5. Nevertheless, according to the DWD 2020, calcium and magnesium salts could be added to condition the water in order to reduce any possible negative health impact, as well as to reduce the corrosiveness or aggressivity of water and to improve taste. This is adjustable by the beverage industry during the brewing process, also to adjust/control the taste of the beer.

With respect to the treatment process efficiency measured as log-reduction values of microbial indicators, the results were limited by their low feedwater concentration. The computed LRVs of *E. coli* varied between > 3.5 and > 5.2 for UF and between 1.8 and > 3.4 for ozonation, both aligned with their indicative LRVs compiled in USEPA (2012). *Clostridium perfringens* and its spores and Somatic coliphages were fully retained by UF whereas ozonation was not fully effective, as expected (USEPA, 2012). Somatic coliphages were not detected in any of the 11 samples analysed.

Regarding trace organics, 25 out of the 54 pharmaceutical compounds analysed were never detected and the remaining were always below the limit of quantification, LOQ (commonly 0.1 to 0.3 µg/L; 1.2 µg/L for Iopromide in scheme 2; 0.6 µg/L for Ciprofloxacin and Iopamidol in scheme 4); 9 per- and polyfluoroalkylated substances (PFAS) were never detected and the remaining 11 were always below LOQ (0.3, 0.6, 1 or 2 ng/L), far below the drinking water quality standard of 100 ng/L for PFAS-total; the ozonation by-product NDMA < 8.4 ng/L, was below the international guidelines. As for regulated oxidation byproducts, haloacetic acids, bromate, chlorate and chlorite were always below LOQ, i.e. 5 HAAs < 1 or 10 µg/L, bromate < 3 µg/L, chlorate < 8 µg/L, chlorite < 5 µg/L; total trihalomethanes varied between < 0.5 µg/L (LOQ) and 1.8 µg/L. Pathogen indicators (of enteric bacteria and viruses, and protozoa) were absent.

Specifically regarding NDMA, the levels observed are far below the USFDA established action level of 5 µg/L in malt beverages sold in the United States (USFDA, 2005), and those of a recent report which presents concentrations ranging between 0.118 and 0.225 µg/L in beer samples from six different countries (ATSDR 2023). Nitrosamines in beer may result from the malt drying process as a result of a reaction between amines, which are naturally present in the barley, and a nitrosating agent, such as nitrogen oxides, which may be present in the air or may be formed during combustion of the fuel used for firing (USFDA, 2005).

4.4.2 Potable reuse schemes

As described in section 3.3.2, four different processes were tested: UF, ozonation, BAC filtration and RO (in two schemes, low-dose chlorination was used downstream the UF for controlling RO biofouling). To ensure a high degree of oxidation of dissolved chemicals, particularly organics, the ozone dose added to the water was 1-2 mg O₃/mg DOC. The BAC filter was then used for uptaking/degrading the oxidized dissolved chemicals remaining in the water (ozonation does not ensure a complete oxidation/mineralization). Due to equipment limitations (it constituted a later upgrade of the pilot unit as explained in Section 3.1.2), it was operated with an empty bed contact time of ca. 5 min. This EBCT is regarded as the minimum, being recommended to operate at 15-30 minutes EBCT to achieve higher removals.

The RO system was operated at 70% WRR and at 60% WRR, and the latter showed better operational results (Table 4.5). 60% WRR corresponded to a permeate flowrate of 1 m³/h and a recirculation flowrate of 0.7 m³/h. An antiscalant (Genesys LF, AUXIAQUA) was added at 3 mg/L (dose recommended by the manufacturer) to prevent the deposit of inorganic components on the RO membranes, thus decreasing the maintenance needs.

During the pilot unit commissioning, biofilm growth in the pipes was observed. To obviate this issue, it was necessary to introduce a pre-treatment (additional barrier), chlorination, to limit the biofilm growth. Nevertheless, it was not possible to fully recover the net permeate flux, and this could have limited the water recovery rates achieved.

A comparison of the main analytical and operational results of the four potable reuse schemes studied (illustrated in Figure 3.5) is presented in Table 4.4 and Table 4.5. In some cases, the values of LOQ varied from one treatment scheme to another due to limitations of the lab to which the analyses were contracted.

Table 4.4 – Comparison of the main analytical results of the four potable reuse schemes studied.

Parameter	Scheme 1	Scheme 2	Scheme 3	Scheme 4
PhC (µg/L) Anastrozole, Atenolol, Azathioprine, Bezafebrate, Buprenorphine, Butorphanol, Capecitabine, Carbamazepine, Chloramphenicol, Citalopram, Clofibrac acid, Cyclobenzaprine, Cyclophosphamide, Diazepam, Enalapril, Fluoxetine, Flutamide, Furosemide, Gabapentin, Hydrochlorothiazide, Ifosfamide, Indomethacin, Ketoprofen, Lincomycin, Loperamide, Metoprolol, Metronidazole, Mycophenolate mofetil, Naproxen, Oxazepam, Paclitaxel, Paracetamol (acetaminophen), Piroxicam, Propranolol, Salbutamol, Sertraline, Sotalol, Sulfamethazine, Sulfamethoxazole, Terbutaline, Thebaine, Tramadol, Trimethoprim, Valsartan, Warfarin, Zolpidem	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Diclofenac	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.150 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Caffeine	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.200 (LOQ)
Gemfibrozil	< 0.200 (LOQ)	< 0.200 (LOQ)	< 0.200 (LOQ)	< 0.200 (LOQ)
Iohexol, Iomeprol	< 0.300 (LOQ)	< 0.300 (LOQ)	< 0.300 (LOQ)	< 0.300 (LOQ)
Ciprofloxacin, Iopamidol	< 0.300 (LOQ)	< 0.300 (LOQ)	< 0.300 (LOQ)	< 0.600 (LOQ)
Iopromide	< 0.300 (LOQ)	< 1.200 (LOQ)	< 0.300 (LOQ)	< 0.300 (LOQ)
Estrogenic hormones (µg/L)				
17-β-estradiol	< 0.100 (LOQ)	<i>n.a.</i>	< 5.000 (LOQ) ^a	< 0.050 (LOQ)
17-α-ethinylestradiol	< 0.100 (LOQ)	<i>n.a.</i>	< 0.050 (LOQ)	< 0.050 (LOQ)
Bisphenol A (µg/L)	< 0.050 (LOQ)	<i>n.a.</i>	< 0.050 (LOQ)	< 0.050 (LOQ)
Alkylphenols (µg/L)				
4-t-Octylphenol, 4-t-Octylphenol diethoxylate, 4-t-Octylphenol monoethoxylate, 4-t-Octylphenol triethoxylate	< 0.010 (LOQ)	<i>n.a.</i>	< 0.010 (LOQ)	< 0.010 (LOQ)
4-n-Octylphenol, 4-Nonylphenol, Nonylphenol (isomer mixture) Nonylphenol diethoxylate (isomer mixture), Nonylphenol monoethoxylate (isomer mixture), Nonylphenol triethoxylate (isomer mixture)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	<i>n.a.</i>	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Sum of 5 OP and OPE	< 0.140 (LOQ)	<i>n.a.</i>	< 0.140 (LOQ)	< 0.140 (LOQ)
Sum of 4 NP and NPE	< 0.40 (LOQ)	<i>n.a.</i>	< 0.40 (LOQ)	< 0.40 (LOQ)
Sum of 5 NP and NPE	< 0.500 (LOQ)	<i>n.a.</i>	< 0.500 (LOQ)	< 0.500 (LOQ)
PFAS (ng/L)				
PFBS, PFDS, PFDA, PFDoDS, PFDoDA, PFHpS, PFHpA, PFHxS, PFHxA, PFNS, PFNA, PFOS, PFOA, PFPeS, PFTTrDA, PFUnDA	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)

Parameter	Scheme 1	Scheme 2	Scheme 3	Scheme 4
PFPeA	< 0.60 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)
PFTTrDS, PFUnDS	< 1.00 (LOQ)	< 1.00 (LOQ)	< 1.00 (LOQ)	< 1.00 (LOQ)
PFBA	< 2.00 (LOQ)	< 2.00 (LOQ)	< 2.00 (LOQ)	< 2.00 (LOQ)
Sum of 20 PFAS	< 9.40 (LOQ)	< 9.10 (LOQ)	< 9.10 (LOQ)	< 9.10 (LOQ)
Bromides (mg/L)	<i>n.a.</i>	< 0.050 (LOQ)	< 0.050 (LOQ)	< 0.050 (LOQ)
Bromates (µg/L)	< 3.0 (LOQ)	< 3.0 (LOQ)	< 3.0 (LOQ)	< 3.0 (LOQ)
Chlorates (µg/L)	< 8.0 (LOQ)	< 8.0 (LOQ)	< 8.0 (LOQ)	< 8.0 (LOQ)
Chlorites (µg/L)	< 5.0 (LOQ)	< 5.0 (LOQ)	< 5.0 (LOQ)	< 5.0 (LOQ)
NDMA (ng/L)	2.84	1.26	8.40	5.61
THM (µg/L)				
Bromodichloromethane	<i>n.a.</i>	0.56	< 0.10 (LOQ)	< 0.10 (LOQ)
Bromoform	<i>n.a.</i>	< 0.20 (LOQ)	< 0.20 (LOQ)	0.26
Chloroform	<i>n.a.</i>	0.85	< 0.10 (LOQ)	0.13
Dibromochloromethane	<i>n.a.</i>	0.19	< 0.10 (LOQ)	< 0.10 (LOQ)
Trihalomethanes - Total	<i>n.a.</i>	1.60	< 0.50 (LOQ)	0.39
HAA (µg/L)				
Bromodichloroacetic Acid, Dibromoacetic Acid, Dibromochloroacetic Acid, Dichloroacetic Acid, Trichloroacetic Acid	<i>n.a.</i>	< 0.50 (LOQ)	< 5.00 (LOQ)	< 0.50 (LOQ)
MBA Acid, MCA Acid	<i>n.a.</i>	< 1.00 (LOQ)	< 10.00 (LOQ)	< 1.00 (LOQ)
Bromochloroacetic Acid	<i>n.a.</i>	< 2.00 (LOQ)	< 20.00 (LOQ)	< 2.00 (LOQ)
Tribromoacetic Acid	<i>n.a.</i>	< 5.00 (LOQ)	< 50.00 (LOQ)	< 5.00 (LOQ)
Sum of 5 HAAs	<i>n.a.</i>	< 1.00 (LOQ)	< 10.00 (LOQ)	< 1.00 (LOQ)
Sum of Chloroacetic Acids	<i>n.a.</i>	< 1.00 (LOQ)	< 10.00 (LOQ)	< 1.00 (LOQ)
Sum of 9 HAAs	<i>n.a.</i>	< 5.00 (LOQ)	< 50.00 (LOQ)	< 5.00 (LOQ)
A254 average [min, max] (cm⁻¹)	0.0011 [0.0004, 0.0017]	0.0023 [< 0.0001, 0.0093]	0.0015 [< 0.0001, 0.0155]	< 0.0001 (LOQ)
A436 average [min, max] (cm⁻¹)	0.0001 [< 0.0001, 0.0003]	0.0007 [< 0.0001, 0.0046]	0.0009 [< 0.0001, 0.0102]	< 0.0001 (LOQ)
TOC average [min, max] (mg C/L)	0.31 [0.19, 0.46]	0.24 [0.10, 0.47]	0.21 [0.11, 0.27]	0.13 [0.06, 0.22]
DOC average [min, max] (mg C/L)	0.31 [0.19, 0.46]	0.24 [0.10, 0.44]	0.21 [0.11, 0.27]	0.13 [0.06, 0.22]
EC @ 20°C average [min, max] (mS/cm)	0.012 [0.001, 0.017]	0.014 [0.001, 0.033]	0.014 [0.010, 0.023]	0.018 [0.016, 0.021]
pH average [min, max] (-)	4.8 [4.6, 5.1]	5.1 [4.5, 5.6]	5.3 [5.1, 5.6]	5.3 [5.2, 5.4]
Transmittance average [min, max] (%)	98.6 [94.7-100.0]	99.3 [97.7-100.0]	99.9 [99.2-100.0]	100
Turbidity average [min, max] (NTU)	0.09 [0.01, 0.10]	0.08 [0.01, 0.30]	0.01 [0.01, 0.03]	0.01 [0.01, 0.01]
Ammoniacal Nitrogen				
average [min, max] (mg NH ₄ /L)	0.06 [< 0.050, 0.10]	0.07 [< 0.031, 0.29]	0.09 [< 0.031, 0.28]	0.27 [0.137, 0.41]
Nitrates average [min, max] (mg NO₃/L)	2.12 [1.04, 3.35]	2.74 [0.38, 3.05]	< 4.00 (LOQ)	< 4.00 (LOQ)
Kjeldahl Nitrogen				
average [min, max] (mg N/L)	< 0.500 (LOQ)	0.50 [< 0.500, 0.55]	< 0.500 (LOQ)	< 0.500 (LOQ)
Total Nitrogen				
average [min, max] (mg N/L)	0.53 [< 0.500, 0.6]	0.54 [< 0.500, 0.92]	0.53 [< 0.500, 0.73]	0.59 [0.52, 0.64]

Parameter	Scheme 1	Scheme 2	Scheme 3	Scheme 4
Total Phosphorus average [min, max] (mg P/L)	< 0.020 (LOQ)	0.02 [< 0.020, 0.02]	< 0.020 (LOQ)	< 0.020 (LOQ)
<i>Escherichia coli</i> (MPN/100 mL)	0	0	0	0
<i>Clostridium perfringens</i> (CFU/100 mL)	0	n.a.	0	0
<i>Clostridium perfringens</i> spores (CFU/50 mL)	0	n.a.	0	0
Somatic coliphages (PFU/mL)	< 1 (LOQ)	n.a.	< 1 (LOQ)	< 1 (LOQ)
F-specific RNA bacteriophages (PFU/mL)	< 1 (LOQ)	n.a.	< 1 (LOQ)	< 1 (LOQ)

n.a. - not measured; < - indicates a below LOQ value

The analytical results obtained showed no advantage in using ozonation (scheme 1) or ozonation + GAC/BAC (scheme 3) in addition to UF (+ Cl₂) + RO (scheme 2). In fact, as stressed in section 4.3.2, the ozonation in schemes 1 and 3 promoted the formation of NDMA, which was only partly removed by the RO ($\leq 50\%$), although to concentrations below the thresholds of 100 ng/L, 10 ng/L and 5 $\mu\text{g/L}$ set for drinking water by WHO (2022), for potable reuse by NWRI-WRRF (2013) guidelines and by USFDA (2015) for malt beverages, respectively.

Table 4.5 – Comparison of the main RO operational results of the four potable reuse schemes studied.

Parameter	Scheme 1	Scheme 2		Scheme 3	Scheme 4
Water recovery rate (%)	70	70	60	60	60
RO feed temperature \pm SD ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	23.8 \pm 1.5	26.2 \pm 1.3	24.6 \pm 2.1	19.6 \pm 1.7	18.5 \pm 1.2
RO feed EC average \pm SD (mS/cm)	1.8 \pm 0.6	1.6 \pm 0.3	2.5 \pm 1.4	1.4 \pm 0.3	1.2 \pm 0.1
RO feed pressure average \pm SD (bar)	11.0 \pm 1.4	11.8 \pm 1.3	9.6 \pm 1.3	11.1 \pm 1.5	11.3 \pm 0.9
RO NDP average \pm SD (bar)	9.2 \pm 1.4	8.5 \pm 0.9	7.0 \pm 0.7	9.5 \pm 1.3	9.4 \pm 0.9
RO normalised flux \pm SD (L/(m ² .h))	21.9 \pm 1.0	20.3 \pm 0.8	17.4 \pm 1.3	20.0 \pm 1.1	20.7 \pm 0.8
Membrane permeability average \pm SD (L/(m ² .h)/bar)	2.4 \pm 0.4	2.4 \pm 0.2	2.5 \pm 0.2	2.1 \pm 0.2	2.2 \pm 0.1

SD: standard deviation

Regarding the operational results, the parameters presented in section 4.3.3 and Table 4.5 show (i) the schemes using ozone (schemes 1, 3 and 4) involved higher net driving pressures (NDPs, needed for ensuring the desired constant RO flux of 21.0 or 16.8 L/(m².h)) and lower membrane permeability (particularly schemes 3 and 4; scheme 1 presented similar average but higher SD) than scheme 2, comprising only UF (and downstream low-dose chlorination for RO biofouling control) and RO, which can be attributed to ozone byproducts formation (Liu et al., 2024), (ii) a higher membrane permeability for scheme 2 operating at 60% water recovery ratio (2.5 \pm 0.2 Lm⁻²h⁻¹bar⁻¹), corresponding also to a lower NDP (7.0 \pm 0.7 bar) despite the higher feed EC.

Further, the pilot demo consisted of an upgrade from a batch demonstration, so no means were available for a full optimization of the operational performance. The BAC was too small and ozonation could not be upgraded to an AOP nor be moved downstream the RO. These changes would have allowed to better understand the need and the gains in water quality and operational performance provided by a final chemical oxidation step after UF + RO.

4.4.3 Operation protocol

Considering (i) the results above, (ii) that the Beirolas WRRF effluent undergoes secondary treatment and sand filtration, (iii) the downstream safety barriers for pathogens and volatile dissolved chemicals control provided by the beer production steps, namely the boiling that sterilizes the wort and

evaporates unwanted volatile compounds, and (iv) taking into account the recommendations from WHO (2017a) and from the State Water Resources Control Board of California (SWRCB, 2024), presented in Chapter 3, overall **scheme 2** exhibits the best performance for this specific pilot demonstration with Beirolas WRRF effluent. In scheme 2, the potable reuse scheme encompasses ultrafiltration with post-chlorination followed by the 3-stage reverse osmosis system (Figure 4.16).

Figure 4.16 – Potable reuse scheme 2 configuration.

In cases where the water is to be stored, an artificial buffer (engineered storage buffer) should be foreseen and, depending on the storage time and conditions (e.g. temperature and light), a final addition of a residual disinfectant, e.g. chlorine, may be needed to assure the microbiological stability of the reclaimed water (avoid microbial regrowth), which would further act as an additional barrier.

Considering the results obtained and explained in Section 4.3, to streamline the water quality monitoring and for the control of hazards of this potable reuse scheme, the following indicators are recommended for regular monitoring (weekly and/or monthly):

- Coliform bacteria or *Escherichia coli* and *Clostridium perfringens* as indicators for enteric bacteria;
- *Clostridium perfringens* spores as an indicator for protozoa;
- Somatic coliphages and bacteriophages as indicators for viruses - the main removal mechanism for viruses is expected to occur through the RO process;
- DOC as indicator of dissolved organics. Selecting multiple chemical indicators with a variety of physicochemical properties will inform on the removal performance of unknown or emerging contaminants and target contaminants with similar properties (Bellona et al., 2004; ATSE, 2013). To facilitate this task, and because most of the emerging contaminants analysed are below the quantification limit, DOC is a possible indicator of dissolved organics and is often monitored for overall treatment performance and for adjusting the treatment operating conditions, e.g. the applied ozone concentration; the RO filtered water is particle free, so DOC equals TOC;
- Electrical conductivity to guarantee the effectiveness of reverse osmosis process (including the RO membrane integrity) on the removal of inorganic compounds and emerging contaminants, the lower the better the effectiveness and the treated water quality.

If ozonation is used, ORP measurements (weekly and/or monthly) should be taken to control and monitor the oxidation of inorganic and organic chemical compounds, and also for inactivation of microbiological microorganisms.

For assessing the water quality compliance, it is recommended to monitor the parameters foreseen in the DWD 2020. Related with the monitoring frequency, the DWD 2020 indicates for a production of 10-100 m³/d (range of the pilot unit) a minimum of two samples per year. For a matter of safety and risk mitigation, and because wastewater is being used, it is recommended to increase the minimum frequency sampling to 12 during the first year of operation (monthly in case of a regular production or seasonally representative) and then analyse the results and propose a new frequency of sampling. The same frequency is proposed for other contaminants, such as pharmaceutical compounds or NDMA.

Table 4.6 lists the key operating conditions and operational guidelines further recommended for the treatment processes studied.

Table 4.6 – Summary of key operating conditions and operational guidelines recommended for the treatment processes studied.

Advanced process	Operation & Maintenance		Control & Monitoring	
	Operation range	Maintenance	Control parameter(s)	Quality parameter(s)
Ozonation	Dose: 1-2 mg O ₃ /mg DOC CT (disinfection): 0.005-0.01 (mg.min/L)/ LRV enteric bacteria	Routine: check for leaks and overheating Preventive maintenance	Ozone concentration	Target contaminants: • Dissolved compound(s) • Pathogens (indicators)
GAC/BAC	EBCT ≥ 5 min (preferably ≥ 15 min) Bed volumes treated: depend on breakthrough target	Backwash (pressure triggered) GAC regeneration (when exhausted)	Operating pressure	Target contaminants: • Dissolved compound(s)
RO	Net driving pressure (NDP): 6-12 bar Permeate flux: 15-25 L/ (m ² .h) Membrane permeability (Lp): 2-3 L/(m ² .h.bar) Antiscalant dosing (dose recommended by manufacturer)	Cartridge (MF) replacement: Inlet pressure drop 0.5 bar Membrane flushing: ~ 1 every 2 weeks Clean-in-place (CIP): • Permeate flow ↓ 10% • Salt Passage ↓ 5-10% • Pressure drop ↑ 10-15%	Conductivity (membrane integrity indicator) DOC (TOC) (dissolved organics indicator)	Target contaminants: • Dissolved compound(s) • Pathogens (indicators)

Regarding the brine stream produced from RO, it could be further processed by ozonation or AOP prior to disposal or recycling to the WRRF water or sludge lines should the volumes or water quality be compatible. Ozonation has proved effectiveness in increasing the biodegradability of RO brine from RO reclamation processes, namely by increasing the BOD₅/TOC ratios by 3.5 times, and with TOC removals up to 25%, with ozone dosages of 10 mg O₃/L (Lee et al., 2009). The brine stream could also be considered for sodium hypochlorite production through electrochlorination, as demonstrated in Alicante Living Lab and is reported in B-WaterSmart D2.9 (Nutrient/brine separation using nitrate-selective EDR membrane and on-site production of sodium hypochlorite from RO brines).

5 Management and communication

Management plans define the necessary actions to be taken in response to incidents and emergencies and are a crucial part of Water Safety Plans for all drinking water supplies (WHO, 2017b). Controlled responses to incidents that may compromise water safety are crucial for protecting public health and maintaining consumer confidence. In many situations, the key to ensure safety will be the implementation of rapid and effective responses. Responses to incidents must be planned, coordinated and executed in a timely and systematic manner (WHO, 2017a).

Potable reuse schemes are complex systems requiring management and operation by highly trained and skilled personnel. It is crucial for managers and operators to have a clear understanding of their roles and responsibilities during routine operations. They should also play an active role in developing criteria for incident response and communication, while fully grasping the implications of non-compliance. Incident and emergency response protocols should be regularly tested to ensure that they are effective and understood. This can involve running mock scenarios (WHO, 2017a).

In the scope of “A reclamation protocol for water reuse in craft beer production”, the adoption of an incident protocol, based on the same principles of Water Safety Plans must be foreseen.

5.1 Incident protocols

Incident protocols for potable reuse schemes should be based on the same principles as protocols for any other type of drinking water system (WHO, 2017b). Points of variation could include consideration of specific characteristics of wastewater influents and wastewater collection systems, trade waste controls, types of treatment processes, possible use of environmental buffers or engineered storages and blending (WHO, 2017a). The purpose of this incident protocol is to outline the procedures and responsibilities to be followed in the event of any incident affecting the safety or quality of reclaimed water produced for craft beer production.

The relevant contents that must be foreseen in the development of incident protocols are:

1. Types of incident:
 - non-compliance with health-based targets;
 - non-compliance with critical limits;
 - accidents/spills that increase levels of contaminants (e.g. discharge of industrial waste into sewage systems);
 - treatment failure;
 - prolonged power outage;
 - extreme weather (e.g. floods, cyclones) and natural disasters (e.g. fires, earthquakes).
2. Assessment of the incident to determine its nature, severity and potential impacts. Incidents will be classified based on their severity level:
 - level 1: Minor incident with minimal impact;
 - level 2: Moderate incident with potential risks to water quality or safety;
 - level 3: Major incident posing significant risks to public health and safety).
3. Reporting requirements

Upon detection of an incident, the designated personnel must immediately notify the Team Leader. The Team Leader will assess the situation and determine the appropriate response actions. Response actions will be tailored to the severity level of the incident and may include:

 - implementing emergency measures to mitigate immediate risks;
 - notifying relevant authorities and stakeholders, particularly, the beer producer;
 - activating backup systems or alternative water sources (Initiating public notification

procedures as necessary – not likely if the reclaimed water is delivered for beer production; needed if/when the reclaimed is to be (also) supplied to final consumers/society).

4. Documentation and Reporting

Detailed records of the incident, response actions and outcomes will be documented. Incident reports will include information on the cause, extent and duration of the incident, as well as any corrective measures taken. Reports will be submitted to regulatory agencies and internal stakeholders as required.

5. Responsibilities of all stakeholders

It will be necessary to establish the different stakeholders and their responsibilities. For example, the wastewater utility, the entity responsible for wastewater collection, the craft beer industry, regulatory authorities, public health agencies and research institutions/academia if necessary. All the relevant stakeholders must have clear roles and responsibilities.

6. Communication protocols and strategies including notification procedures

Communication protocols should be developed and established to define clear communication channels, roles and responsibilities for all stakeholders, including internal staff, regulatory agencies, emergency responders and the craft beer industry. A designated primary contact person or team should be responsible for receiving and disseminating notifications. Additionally, it is recommended to create pre-approved templates for public notifications, such as advisories, alerts and press releases, to maintain consistency and accuracy of information.

7. Emergency contact list.

5.2 Reviewing of incidents protocols

Regular reviews of incident protocols are essential to ensure their effectiveness, typically conducted annually. The primary goals of these protocols are to safeguard the water used in beer production and minimize the occurrence and impact of hazardous events and incidents. Incident reports should be carefully evaluated to identify recurring incident types, which may indicate reliability issues; then, in case of such evidence, the protocols must be reviewed. These reviews should entail thorough investigations of the incidents and responses. Also, protocol content should be periodically reviewed to ensure they are updated with respect to treatment processes, operational monitoring, critical limits, verification procedures and water quality standards. Updates should also include contact personnel information.

5.3 Communication

Effective communication plays a vital role in handling incidents, guaranteeing specific and coordinated responses to maintain consumer confidence and trust. When it is necessary to deal with an incident, there are some answers that must be communicated to the other stakeholders: what happened? when did it occur? what is being done to solve the situation?

When the consumer is an industrial customer, as the beer producer, public notification is likely not necessary (Section 5.1). If/when public supply of reclaimed water is (also) considered, incident protocols should identify communication responsibilities and include who makes the decision about public notification of incidents and leads communication. In many cases, there may be joint responsibilities, for example, the health agency will take the lead on public health matters while the reclaimed water supplier will take the lead on operational responses, including repairs and delivery of alternative sources of water. These responsibilities need to be clearly described and understood.

6 Conclusions

Potable reuse can provide a realistic and practical source of drinking water under various circumstances and pilot demonstration projects are essential for developing future guidelines and best practices. The work conducted within task 2.4.1 of the B-WaterSmart project contributed with pilot field data to the development of such guidelines, focusing on water quality and potable reuse schemes' operation and redundancy for the safe production, from municipal wastewater, of water with adequate quality to be used in craft beer production. This involves direct potable reuse (DPR) applications with additional downstream safety barriers (provided by the beer production steps). The goal is to establish DPR as a solution for aggravated water scarcity, localized needs, emergency situations, and to build societal trust in water reuse safety.

A pilot unit was installed at the Beirolas Water Resource Recovery Facility (WRRF) in Portugal, with tertiary treatment and sand filtration. Four advanced treatment technologies were pilot tested – ultrafiltration (UF), ozonation (O₃), biologically active granular activated carbon (BAC) filtration, and reverse osmosis (RO), and four different RO-based potable reuse schemes were continuously piloted (24/7) and compared towards water quality and operational performance: (1) UF+O₃+RO, (2) UF(+Cl₂)+RO, (3) UF(+Cl₂)+O₃+BAC+RO, (4) O₃+BAC+RO. In treatment schemes 2 and 3, low-dose chlorination was used downstream the UF for controlling RO biofouling.

All four multi-barrier potable reuse schemes produced water of sufficient quality to be reused in the beverage industry, complying with EU and Portuguese drinking water standards. Pathogen indicators were absent, and levels of PFAS, disinfection byproducts, and pharmaceutical compounds were below the quantification limits (PFAS < 0.3, 0.6, 1 or 2 ng/L, 5 HAAs < 1 µg/L, bromate < 3 µg/L, chlorate < 8 µg/L, chlorite < 5 µg/L, PhCs < 0.1 to 1.2 µg/L). Total THMs varied between < 0.5 µg/L (LOQ) and 1.8 µg/L (far below the DWD 2020 parametric value) and NDMA was below the international guidelines.

Operational monitoring results indicated lower normalized net driving pressure, i.e. lower energy demand, for the potable reuse 2. Thus, considering the results obtained and the downstream safety barriers provided by the beer production steps (including boiling) for controlling pathogens and volatile dissolved chemicals, the scheme comprising UF (+Cl₂, whenever needed for RO biofouling control) + RO should be adequate for this specific application. In cases where the water is to be stored, an artificial buffer (engineered storage buffer) should be foreseen and, depending on the storage time and conditions, a final chlorination may be needed to assure the microbiological stability of the reclaimed water, which would further act as an additional barrier.

Based on the results obtained:

- Microbiological and chemical water quality indicators were recommended for regular monitoring to streamline water quality monitoring and control hazards;
- A water quality monitoring programme was proposed, including parameters, location and sample frequency.

Also, effective management and communication are crucial for potable reuse in craft beer production, requiring skilled personnel for routine operations and emergencies. Protocols must align with drinking water safety plans, consider specific wastewater characteristics, and be regularly updated. They should define procedures, responsibilities, severity assessments, reporting requirements, and involve stakeholders like the wastewater utility, beer producer, and competent authorities.

7 References

- Angelakis A.N., Gikas P. (2014). Water reuse: Overview of current practices and trends in the world with emphasis on EU states. *Water Utility Journal*, 8: 67-78.
- APA (2019). Guia para a Reutilização de Água – Usos não potáveis. Agência Portuguesa do Ambiente. Outubro. 193 pp.
- APHA-AWWA-WEF (1998). Standard Methods for the Examination of Water and Wastewater (20th ed.). Clesceri L., Greenberg A., Eaton A. Eds. American Public Health Association, American Waer Works Association, Water Environment Federation. Washington, DC. p. 1495–6.
- ATSDR (2023). Toxicological profile for *N*-Nitrosodimethylamine (NDMA). Agency for Toxic Substances and Disease Registry. Atlanta, GA: U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, Public Health Service.
- ATSE (2013). Drinking water through recycling - The benefits and costs of supplying direct to the distribution system. A report of a study by the Australian Academy of Technological Sciences and Engineering. S. Khan principal author. Melbourne, Australia. October. ISBN 978 1 921388 25 5
- Bartram J., Corrales L., Davison A., Deere D., Drury D., Gordon B., Howard G., Rinehold A., Stevens M. (2009). Water safety plan manual: Step-by-step risk management for drinking-water suppliers. World Health Organization. Geneva.
- Bellona C., Drewes J.E., Xu P., Amy G. (2004). Factors affecting the rejection of organic solutes during NF/RO treatment – a literature review. *Water Research*, 38(12): 2795-2809.
- Bruce G.M., Pleus R.C., Snyder S.A. (2010). Toxicological relevance of pharmaceuticals in drinking-water. *Environmental Science & Technology*. 44(14): 5619–5626.
- Bull R.J., Crook J., Whittaker M., Cotruvo J.A. (2011). Therapeutic dose as the point of departure in assessing the health hazards from drugs in drinking-water and recycled municipal wastewater. *Regulatory Toxicology and Pharmacology*. 60:1–19
- C40 Cities and Arup (2016) Deadline 2020: How cities will get the job done.
- Cardoso M.A., Rosa M.J., Ribeiro R., van Dam A., Glotzbach R., Martín (UNED)J., De Paepe S., Quina A., Kruse J., Hein A., Wencki K., Conrad A., Kramer A., Gomes C., Schmidt L. (2024). Guidelines & recommendations for regulation and policy instruments. B-WaterSmart D5.6. February, 96 pp.
- Cordeiro S., Ferrario F., Pereira H.X., Ferreira F., Matos, J.S. (2023). Water reuse, a sustainable alternative in the context of water scarcity and climate change in the Lisbon Metropolitan Area. *Sustainability*, 15(16), 12578. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su151612578>
- Decreto-Lei n.º 119/2019, de 21 de agosto. Estabelece o regime jurídico de produção de água para reutilização, obtida a partir do tratamento de águas residuais, bem como da sua utilização. <https://diariodarepublica.pt/dr/detalhe/decreto-lei/119-2019-124097549>
- Decreto-Lei n.º 69/2023, de 21 de agosto, Estabelece o regime jurídico da qualidade da água destinada ao consumo humano, transpondo diversas diretivas. <https://diariodarepublica.pt/dr/detalhe/decreto-lei/69-2023-220113533>
- ERSAR (2022). Relatório anual dos serviços de águas e resíduos em Portugal – Volume 1 – Caraterização geral do setor de águas e resíduos. Entidade Reguladora dos Serviços de Águas e Resíduos. Lisboa.
- European Commission, Joint Research Centre (2018). Guidebook 'How to develop a Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan (SECAP)'. Part 1, The SECAP process, step-by-step towards

- low carbon and climate resilient cities by 2030, P.Bertoldi,(editor) Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg.
- EU (2000). Directive 2000/60/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 October 2000 establishing a framework for Community action in the field of water policy. <http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2000/60/oj>
- EU (2020a). Regulation (EU) 2020/741 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 May 2020 on minimum requirements for water reuse. <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2020/741/oj>
- EU (2020b). Directive (EU) 2020/2184 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2020 on the quality of water intended for human consumption (recast). <http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2020/2184/oj>
- EU (2024). Proposal for a Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council concerning urban wastewater treatment (recast). 6848/24.
- GovPT (2019). Reutilização dos efluentes é fundamental para poupar água potável. XXI GOVERNO - REPÚBLICA PORTUGUESA. www.portugal.gov.pt/pt/gc21/comunicacao/noticia?i=reutilizacao-dos-efluentes-e-fundamental-para-poupar-agua-potavel. Accessed on 9 may 2024
- Hrudey S.E., Hrudey E.J. (2004a). Safe drinking-water: Lessons from recent outbreaks in affluent nations. London: IWA Publishing. Also published in *Occupational Medicine*, 55(8): 643–644
- Hrudey S.E., Hrudey E.J. (2014b). Ensuring safe drinking-water: Learning from frontline experience with contamination. American Water Works Association. Denver, USA.
- IPCC (2014). Climate Change 2014: Synthesis Report. Contribution of Working Groups I, II and III to the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change [Core Writing Team, R.K. Pachauri and L.A. Meyer (eds.)]. Geneva, Switzerland, 151 pp.
- ISO 16075-2:2020. Guidelines for treated wastewater use for irrigation projects. Part 2: Development of the project. International Standardization Organization. Geneva. Switzerland.
- ISO 20426:2018. Guidelines for health risk assessment and management for non-potable water reuse. International Standardization Organization. Geneva. Switzerland.
- ISO 20468-1:2018. Guidelines for performance evaluation of treatment technologies for water reuse systems - Part 1: General. International Standardization Organization. Geneva. Switzerland.
- Jeffrey P., Yang Z., Judd S.J. (2022). The status of potable water reuse implementation. *Water Research*. 214, 118198.
- Lazarova V., Asano T., Bahri A., Anderson J. Eds. (2013). Milestones in water reuse. The Best success stories. IWA publishing, London, UK.
- Lai Y.L., Ng H.Y., Ong S.L., Hu J.Y., Tao G., Kekre K., Viswanath B., Lay W., Seah H. (2009). Ozone-biological activated carbon as a pretreatment process for reverse osmosis brine treatment and recovery. *Water Research*, 43(16), 3948-3955.
- Leverenz H.L., Tchobanoglous G., Asano T. (2011). Direct potable reuse: A future imperative. *Journal of Water Reuse and Desalination*. 1: 2–10.
- Lisbon Municipality (2024). Water reuse plan allows for potential savings of up to 3 million m³. News Published on the Municipality's Website. Available online: <https://www.lisboa.pt/actualidade/noticias/detalhe/plano-de-reutilizacao-de-agua-permite-poupar3-milhoes-de-m3-de-agua-potavel> (accessed on 9 may 2024).
- Liu Y., Guo Y., Yin Z., Yang W. (2024). Insights into coagulation, softening and ozonation pre-treatments for reverse osmosis membrane fouling control in reclamation of textile secondary effluent. *Journal of Water Process Engineering*, 58, 104764.

- MacKenzie W.R., Hoxie N.J., Proctor M.E., Gradus M.S., Blair K.A., Peterson D.E., Kazmierczak J.J., Addis D.G., Fox K.R., Rose J.B., Davis J.P. (1994). A massive outbreak in Milwaukee of *Cryptosporidium* infection transmitted through the public water supply. *New England Journal of Medicine*. 331: 161–167.
- Munné A., Solà C., Ejarque E., Sanchís J., Serra P., Corbella I., Aceves M., Galofré B., Boleda M.R., Paraira M., Molist J. (2023). Indirect potable water reuse to face drought events in Barcelona city. Setting a monitoring procedure to protect aquatic ecosystems and to ensure a safe drinking water supply. *Science of The Total Environment*. 866: 161339.
- NRMMCEPHCNHMRC (2006–2009). Australian guidelines for water recycling: Managing health and environmental risks [Phase 1 (2006), Phase 2 (2008, 2009)]. National Resource Management Ministerial Council, Environment Protection and Heritage Council, National Health and Medical Research Council, Australian Government.
- NWRI-WRRF (2013). Examining the criteria for direct potable reuse. National Water Research Institute 2013-01, WaterReuse Research Foundation 11-02.
- Oliveira R. (2021). Study of the current and future water availability in Portugal. In *Water Availability and Climate Change Conference*, Lisbon 7th December.
- Pecson B., Trussell R.S., Pisarenko A., Trussell R.R. (2015). Achieving reliability in potable reuse: The Four Rs. *Journal of American Water Works Association*. 107(3): 48–58.
- Schwab B.W., Hayes E.P., Fiori J.M., Mastrocco F.L., Roden N.M., Cragin D., Meyerhoff R.D., D'Aco V.J., Anderson P.D. (2005). Human pharmaceuticals in US surface waters: A human health risk assessment. *Regulatory Toxicology and Pharmacology*. 42(3): 296–312.
- Snyder S.A., Trenholm R.A., Snyder E.M., Bruce G.M., Pleus R.C., Hemming J.D.C. (2008). Toxicological relevance of EDCs and pharmaceuticals in drinking-water. AWWA Research Foundation, Denver (CO), USA.
- SWRCB (2024) Direct Potable Reuse Regulations (SBDDW-23-001) State Water Resources Control Board. California, USA. https://www.waterboards.ca.gov/drinking_water/certlic/drinkingwater/documents/direct_potable_reuse/sbddw-23-001-dpr-reg-text-oal-final.pdf (accessed on 14 October 2024).
- Tchobanoglous G., Cotruvo J., Crook J., McDonald E., Olivieri A., Salveson A., Trussell R.S. (2015). Framework for direct potable reuse. WaterReuse Research Foundation. Water Environment Federation, American Water Works Association, National Water Research Institute. WaterReuseproject number 14-20. Alexandria (VA), USA. ISBN: 978-1-941242-30-8.
- UNDESA (2014). World urbanization prospects. United Nations, Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Population Division.
- UNESCO World Water Assessment Programme (2009). Water in a changing world. The United Nations World Water Development Report 3. United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization, Paris and London. ISBN: 978-9-23104-095-5
- USEPA (1974). Design criteria for mechanical electric and fluid system and component reliability. Office of Water Program Operators. Federal Water Quality Administration. United States Environmental Protection Agency. EPA-430-99-74-001. Washington (DC), USA.
- USEPA (2005). Membrane filtration guidance manual. EPA 815-R-06-009. Washington (DC): United States Environmental Protection Agency.
- USEPA (2012). Guidelines for Water Reuse. United States Environmental Protection Agency, Office of Wastewater Management, Office of Water. EPA/600/R-12/618. Washington (DC), USA.

- USEPA (2017). 2017 Potable reuse compendium. United States Environmental Protection Agency. Washington (DC), USA.
- USEPA (2019). Water Reuse Action Plan. <https://www.epa.gov/waterreuse/water-reuse-action-plan>
- USFDA (2005). CPG Sec 510.600: Dimethylnitrosamine in malt beverages. U.S. Food and Drug Administration. <https://www.fda.gov/regulatory-information/search-fda-guidance-documents/cpgsec-510600-dimethylnitrosamine-malt-beverages>. Accessed on 14 October 2024.
- Viegas R. M. C., Sousa A., Póvoa P., Martins J., Rosa M. J. (2011). Treated wastewater use in Portugal: challenges and opportunities. In Proc. WATERuse 2011 – 8th International Conference on Water Reclamation and Reuse, IWA. Barcelona, Sept.
- Viegas R.M.C., Mesquita E., Inocêncio P., Teixeira A.P., Martins J., Rosa M.J. (2015). Water reclamation with hybrid coagulation–ceramic microfiltration: first part of a long-term pilot study in Portugal. *Journal of Water Reuse and Desalination* 5(4) 550-556. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wrd.2015.122>
- Viegas R.M.C., Mesquita E., Campinas, M., Rosa M.J. (2020). Pilot studies and cost analysis of hybrid powdered activated carbon/ceramic microfiltration for controlling pharmaceutical compounds and organic matter in water reclamation. *Water* 12(1) 33. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w12010033>
- WaterReuse Research Foundation, American Water Works Association, Water Environment Federation, & National Water Research Institute. (2015). Framework for direct potable reuse (J. J. Mosher & G. M. Vartanian, Eds.).
- WHO (2012). Pharmaceuticals in drinking-water. World Health Organization. Geneva. Switzerland. http://www.who.int/water_sanitation_health/publications/pharmaceuticals-in-drinking-water/en/
- WHO (2017a). Potable reuse: Guidance for producing safe drinking-water. World Health Organization. Geneva. Switzerland.
- WHO (2017b). Guidelines for Drinking-water Quality, 4th edition incorporating the first addendum. World Health Organization. Geneva. Switzerland. http://www.who.int/water_sanitation_health/publications/drinking-water-quality-guidelines-4-including-1st-addendum/en/
- WHO (2022). Guidelines for drinking-water quality: fourth edition incorporating the first and second addenda. World Health Organization. Geneva. Switzerland. Licence: CC BY-NC-SA 3.0 IGO.

ANNEX I – Summary of all analytical results

Table I.1 – Main analytical results of potable reuse scheme 1 (outlet concentrations of each treatment process).

Parameter	UF	O3	RO
PhC (µg/L)			
Anastrozole	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Atenolol	0.156	0.104	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Azathioprine	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Bezafibrate	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Buprenorphine	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Butorphanol	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Caffeine	0.175	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Capecitabine	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Carbamazepine	0.511	0.150	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Chloramphenicol	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Ciprofloxacin	0.444	0.387	< 0.300 (LOQ)
Citalopram	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Clofibric acid	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Cyclobenzaprine	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Cyclophosphamide	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Diazepam	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Diclofenac	2.840	0.714	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Enalapril	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Fluoxetine	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Flutamide	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Furosemide	0.798	0.123	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Gabapentin	1.170	1.000	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Gemfibrozil	< 0.200 (LOQ)	< 0.200 (LOQ)	< 0.200 (LOQ)
Hydrochlorothiazide	2.720	1.910	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Ifosfamide	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Indomethacin	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Iohexol	< 0.300 (LOQ)	< 0.300 (LOQ)	< 0.300 (LOQ)
Iomeprol	0.921	0.668	< 0.300 (LOQ)
Iopamidol	0.429	< 0.300 (LOQ)	< 0.300 (LOQ)
Iopromide	2.290	2.230	< 0.300 (LOQ)
Ketoprofen	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Lincomycin	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Loperamide	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Metoprolol	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Metronidazole	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Mycophenolate mofetil	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Naproxen	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Oxazepam	0.252	0.180	< 0.100 (LOQ)

Parameter	UF	O3	RO
Paclitaxel	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Paracetamol (acetaminophen)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Piroxicam	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Propranolol	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Salbutamol	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Sertraline	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Sotalol	0.293	0.115	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Sulfamethazine	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Sulfamethoxazole	0.423	0.154	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Terbutaline	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Thebaine	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Tramadol	0.555	0.367	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Trimethoprim	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Valsartan	0.416	0.280	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Warfarin	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Zolpidem	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Estrogenic hormones (µg/L)			
17-β-estradiol	< 0.100 (LOQ)	<i>n.a.</i>	< 0.100 (LOQ)
17-α-ethinylestradiol	< 0.100 (LOQ)	<i>n.a.</i>	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Bisphenol A (µg/L)			
	< 0.050 (LOQ)	< 0.050 (LOQ)	< 0.050 (LOQ)
Alkylphenols (µg/L)			
4-n-Octylphenol	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
4-Nonylphenol	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
4-t-Octylphenol	< 0.010 (LOQ)	< 0.010 (LOQ)	< 0.010 (LOQ)
4-t-Octylphenol diethoxylate	< 0.010 (LOQ)	< 0.010 (LOQ)	< 0.010 (LOQ)
4-t-Octylphenol monoethoxylate	< 0.010 (LOQ)	< 0.010 (LOQ)	< 0.010 (LOQ)
4-t-Octylphenol triethoxylate	< 0.010 (LOQ)	< 0.010 (LOQ)	< 0.010 (LOQ)
Nonylphenol (isomer mixture)	< 0.140 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Nonylphenol diethoxylate (isomer mixture)	< 0.110 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Nonylphenol monoethoxylate (isomer mixture)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Nonylphenol triethoxylate (isomer mixture)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Sum of 5 OP and OPE	< 0.140 (LOQ)	< 0.140 (LOQ)	< 0.140 (LOQ)
Sum of 4 NP and NPE	< 0.41 (LOQ)	< 0.40 (LOQ)	< 0.40 (LOQ)
Sum of 5 NP and NPE	< 0.550 (LOQ)	< 0.500 (LOQ)	< 0.500 (LOQ)
PFAS (ng/L)			
Perfluorobutane sulfonic acid (PFBS)	< 3.90 (LOQ)	3.57	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluorobutanoic acid (PFBA)	< 28.0 (LOQ)	< 32.0 (LOQ)	< 2.0 (LOQ)
Perfluorodecane sulfonic acid (PFDS)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluorodecanoic acid (PFDA)	0.37	0.38	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluorododecane sulfonic acid (PFDoDS)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluorododecanoic acid (PFDoDA)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluoroheptane sulfonic acid (PFHpS)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluoroheptanoic acid (PFHpA)	2.55	2.51	< 0.30 (LOQ)

Parameter	UF	O3	RO
Perfluorohexane sulfonic acid (PFHxS)	1.06	1.00	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluorohexanoic acid (PFHxA)	6.29	5.80	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluorononane sulfonic acid (PFNS)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluorononanoic acid (PFNA)	0.57	0.56	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluorooctane sulfonic acid (PFOS)	2.80	2.79	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA)	5.91	5.53	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluoropentane sulfonic acid (PFPeS)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluoropentanoic acid (PFPeA)	6.42	7.28	< 0.60 (LOQ)
Perfluorotridecane sulfonic acid (PFTTrDS)	< 1.0 (LOQ)	< 1.0 (LOQ)	< 1.0 (LOQ)
Perfluorotridecanoic acid (PFTTrDA)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluoroundecane sulfonic acid (PFUnDS)	< 1.0 (LOQ)	< 1.0 (LOQ)	< 1.0 (LOQ)
Perfluoroundecanoic acid (PFUnDA)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Sum of 20 PFAS (2020/2184)	26.00	29.40	< 9.40 (LOQ)
Bromides (mg/L)	0.857	<i>n.a.</i>	<i>n.a.</i>
Bromates (µg/L)	< 9.0 (LOQ)	< 6.0 (LOQ)	< 3.0 (LOQ)
Chlorates (µg/L)	167	67	< 8.0 (LOQ)
Chlorites (µg/L)	< 15.0 (LOQ)	< 10.0 (LOQ)	< 5.0 (LOQ)
NDMA (ng/L)	2.34	4.02	2.84
A254 average [min, max] (cm⁻¹)	0.1745 [0.1416, 0.2081]	0.1365 [0.0624, 0.1628]	0.0011 [0.0004, 0.0017]
A436 average [min, max] (cm⁻¹)	0.0141 [0.0094, 0.0164]	0.0082 [< 0.0001, 0.0163]	0.0001 [< 0.0001, 0.0003]
TOC average [min, max] (mg C/L)	5.79 [4.36, 6.69]	5.43 [4.47, 6.31]	0.31 [0.19, 0.46]
DOC average [min, max] (mg C/L)	5.65 [4.20, 6.60]	5.45 [4.47, 6.31]	0.31 [0.19, 0.46]
EC @ 20°C average [min, max] (mS/cm)	0.93 [0.76, 1.44]	0.93 [0.77, 1.41]	0.012 [0.001, 0.017]
pH average [min, max] (-)	6.6 [6.6, 6.9]	6.8 [6.7, 7.0]	4.8 [4.6, 5.1]
Transmittance average [min, max] (%)	67.0 [61.7, 73.6]	73.1 [68.7, 83.9]	98.6 [94.7, 100.0]
Turbidity average [min, max] (NTU)	0.24 [0.10, 1.00]	0.13 [0.10, 0.20]	0.09 [0.01, 0.10]
Ammoniacal Nitrogen average [min, max] (mg NH₄/L)	0.13 [< 0.050, 0.40]	0.33 [< 0.050, 1.40]	0.06 [< 0.050, 0.10]
Nitrates average [min, max] (mg NO₃/L)	46.10 [15.00, 67.10]	57.38 [41.00, 67.10]	2.12 [1.04, 3.35]
Kjeldahl Nitrogen average [min, max] (mg N/L)	0.86 [< 0.500, 1.10]	0.91 [< 0.500, 1.20]	< 0.500 (LOQ)
Total Nitrogen average [min, max] (mg N/L)	14.00 [12.00, 16.00]	14.40 [12.00, 16.00]	0.53 [< 0.500, 0.6]

Parameter	UF	O3	RO
Total Phosphorus average [min, max] (mg P/L)	4.42 [4.10, 5.10]	5.00 [4.20, 5.60]	< 0.020 (LOQ)
<i>Escherichia coli</i> (MPN/100 mL)	0	0	0
<i>Clostridium perfringens</i> (CFU/100 mL)	0	0	0
<i>Clostridium perfringens</i> spores (CFU/50 mL)	0	0	0
Somatic coliphages (PFU/mL)	< 1 (LOQ)	< 1 (LOQ)	< 1 (LOQ)
F-specific RNA bacteriophages (PFU/mL)	< 1 (LOQ)	< 1 (LOQ)	< 1 (LOQ)
Ecotoxicology (%)			
Daphnia magna Immobilization (original sample)	8.3	8.3	8.3
<i>Vibrio fischeri</i> Inhibition for dilution 800 mL/L	16.6	-3.9	1.1

n.a. - not measured; < - indicates a below LOQ value

Table I.2 – Main analytical results of potable reuse scheme 2 (outlet concentrations of each treatment process).

Parameter	UF	O3
PhC (µg/L)		
Anastrozole	< 0.010 (LOQ)	< 0.010 (LOQ)
Atenolol	0.076	< 0.010 (LOQ)
Azathioprine	< 0.010 (LOQ)	< 0.010 (LOQ)
Bezafibrate	0.010	< 0.010 (LOQ)
Buprenorphine	< 0.010 (LOQ)	< 0.010 (LOQ)
Butorphanol	< 0.010 (LOQ)	< 0.010 (LOQ)
Caffeine	0.019	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Capecitabine	< 0.020 (LOQ)	< 0.020 (LOQ)
Carbamazepine	0.612	< 0.010 (LOQ)
Chloramphenicol	< 0.010 (LOQ)	< 0.010 (LOQ)
Ciprofloxacin	0.033	< 0.060 (LOQ)
Citalopram	0.068	< 0.010 (LOQ)
Clofibric acid	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Cyclobenzaprine	< 0.010 (LOQ)	< 0.010 (LOQ)
Cyclophosphamide	< 0.050 (LOQ)	< 0.050 (LOQ)
Diazepam	< 0.010 (LOQ)	< 0.010 (LOQ)
Diclofenac	2.180	< 0.150 (LOQ)
Enalapril	< 0.010 (LOQ)	< 0.010 (LOQ)
Fluoxetine	0.029	< 0.010 (LOQ)
Flutamide	< 0.010 (LOQ)	< 0.010 (LOQ)
Furosemide	0.404	< 0.050 (LOQ)
Gabapentin	0.596	< 0.010 (LOQ)
Gemfibrozil	< 0.050 (LOQ)	< 0.050 (LOQ)
Hydrochlorothiazide	2.670	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Ifosfamide	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)

Parameter	UF	O3
Indomethacin	0.030	< 0.010 (LOQ)
Iohexol	< 0.300 (LOQ)	< 0.300 (LOQ)
Iomeprol	3.830	< 0.300 (LOQ)
Iopamidol	0.795	< 0.300 (LOQ)
Iopromide	3.620	< 1.20 (LOQ)
Ketoprofen	0.026	< 0.050 (LOQ)
Lincomycin	< 0.010 (LOQ)	< 0.010 (LOQ)
Loperamide	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Metoprolol	0.044	< 0.010 (LOQ)
Metronidazole	0.040	< 0.010 (LOQ)
Mycophenolate mofetil	< 0.010 (LOQ)	< 0.010 (LOQ)
Naproxen	< 0.050 (LOQ)	< 0.050 (LOQ)
Oxazepam	0.214	< 0.010 (LOQ)
Paclitaxel	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Paracetamol (acetaminophen)	< 0.050 (LOQ)	< 0.050 (LOQ)
Piroxicam	< 0.010 (LOQ)	< 0.010 (LOQ)
Propranolol	0.056	< 0.010 (LOQ)
Salbutamol	< 0.010 (LOQ)	< 0.010 (LOQ)
Sertraline	0.055	< 0.010 (LOQ)
Sotalol	0.326	< 0.010 (LOQ)
Sulfamethazine	< 0.050 (LOQ)	< 0.050 (LOQ)
Sulfamethoxazole	0.490	< 0.010 (LOQ)
Terbutaline	< 0.010 (LOQ)	< 0.010 (LOQ)
Thebaine	< 0.010 (LOQ)	< 0.010 (LOQ)
Tramadol	0.766	< 0.010 (LOQ)
Trimethoprim	0.059	< 0.010 (LOQ)
Valsartan	0.200	< 0.050 (LOQ)
Warfarin	< 0.010 (LOQ)	< 0.010 (LOQ)
Zolpidem	< 0.010 (LOQ)	< 0.010 (LOQ)
PFAS (ng/L)		
Perfluorobutane sulfonic acid (PFBS)	1.02	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluorobutanoic acid (PFBA)	< 14.0 (LOQ)	< 2.0 (LOQ)
Perfluorodecane sulfonic acid (PFDS)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluorodecanoic acid (PFDA)	0.31	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluorododecane sulfonic acid (PFDoDS)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluorododecanoic acid (PFDoDA)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluoroheptane sulfonic acid (PFHpS)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluoroheptanoic acid (PFHpA)	2.39	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluorohexane sulfonic acid (PFHxS)	0.82	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluorohexanoic acid (PFHxA)	5.84	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluorononane sulfonic acid (PFNS)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluorononanoic acid (PFNA)	0.53	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluorooctane sulfonic acid (PFOS)	2.00	< 0.30 (LOQ)

Parameter	UF	O3
Perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA)	2.66	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluoropentane sulfonic acid (PFPeS)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluoropentanoic acid (PFPeA)	6.00	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluorotridecane sulfonic acid (PFTrDS)	< 1.0 (LOQ)	< 1.0 (LOQ)
Perfluorotridecanoic acid (PFTrDA)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluoroundecane sulfonic acid (PFUnDS)	< 1.0 (LOQ)	< 1.0 (LOQ)
Perfluoroundecanoic acid (PFUnDA)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Sum of 20 PFAS (2020/2184)	21.60	< 9.10 (LOQ)
Bromides (mg/L)	0.185	< 0.050 (LOQ)
Bromates (µg/L)	< 3.0 (LOQ)	< 3.0 (LOQ)
Chlorates (µg/L)	192	< 8.0 (LOQ)
Chlorites (µg/L)	< 5.0 (LOQ)	< 5.0 (LOQ)
NDMA (ng/L)	2.61	1.26
THM (µg/L)		
Bromodichloromethane	2.06	0.56
Bromoform	< 0.20 (LOQ)	< 0.20 (LOQ)
Chloroform	5.81	0.85
Dibromochloromethane	0.76	0.19
Trihalomethanes - Total	8.63	1.60
HAA (µg/L)		
Bromochloroacetic Acid	< 2.0 (LOQ)	< 2.0 (LOQ)
Bromodichloroacetic Acid	0.95	< 0.50 (LOQ)
Dibromoacetic Acid	< 0.50 (LOQ)	< 0.50 (LOQ)
Dibromochloroacetic Acid	< 0.50 (LOQ)	< 0.50 (LOQ)
Dichloroacetic Acid	< 0.50 (LOQ)	< 0.50 (LOQ)
Monobromoacetic Acid	< 1.0 (LOQ)	< 1.0 (LOQ)
Monochloroacetic Acid	< 1.0 (LOQ)	< 1.0 (LOQ)
Tribromoacetic Acid	< 5.0 (LOQ)	< 5.0 (LOQ)
Trichloroacetic Acid	2.55	< 0.50 (LOQ)
Sum of 5 HAAs	2.60	< 1.0 (LOQ)
Sum of 9 HAAs	< 5.0 (LOQ)	< 5.0 (LOQ)
Sum of Chloroacetic Acids	2.60	< 1.0 (LOQ)
A254 average [min, max] (cm⁻¹)	0.1599 [0.1352, 0.1806]	0.0023 [< 0.0001, 0.0093]
A436 average [min, max] (cm⁻¹)	0.0126 [0.0062, 0.0173]	0.0007 [< 0.0001, 0.0046]
TOC average [min, max] (mg C/L)	4.99 [2.22, 8.80]	0.24 [0.10, 0.47]
DOC average [min, max] (mg C/L)	5.25 [2.22, 12.50]	0.24 [0.10, 0.44]
EC @ 20°C average [min, max] (mS/cm)	1.078 [0.572, 3.082]	0.014 [0.001, 0.033]

Parameter	UF	O3
pH average [min, max] (-)	6.9 [6.6, 7.3]	5.1 [4.5, 5.6]
Transmittance average [min, max] (%)	70.0 [64.9, 98.1]	99.3 [97.7, 100.0]
Turbidity average [min, max] (NTU)	0.12 [0.01, 0.40]	0.08 [0.01, 0.30]
Ammoniacal Nitrogen average [min, max] (mg NH ₄ /L)	1.29 [< 0.031, 10.00]	0.07 [< 0.031, 0.29]
Nitrates average [min, max] (mg NO ₃ /L)	28.47 [4.00, 65.20]	2.74 [0.38, 3.05]
Kjeldahl Nitrogen average [min, max] (mg N/L)	1.91 [< 0.500, 7.40]	0.50 [< 0.500, 0.55]
Total Nitrogen average [min, max] (mg N/L)	11.10 [6.30, 17.00]	0.54 [< 0.500, 0.92]
Total Phosphorus average [min, max] (mg P/L)	3.21 [0.16, 5.40]	0.02 [< 0.020, 0.02]
Escherichia coli (MPN/100 mL)	0	0
Ecotoxicology (%)		
Daphnia magna Immobilization (original sample)	8.3	0
Vibrio fischeri Inhibition for dilution 800 mL/L	-2.3	2.3

n.a. - not measured; < - indicates a below LOQ value

Table I.3 – Main analytical results of potable reuse scheme 3 (outlet concentrations of each treatment process).

Parameter	UF	O3	BAC	RO
PhC (µg/L)				
Anastrozole	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Atenolol	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Azathioprine	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Bezafibrate	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Buprenorphine	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Butorphanol	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Caffeine	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Capecitabine	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Carbamazepine	0.598	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Chloramphenicol	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Ciprofloxacin	0.868	< 0.300 (LOQ)	< 0.300 (LOQ)	< 0.300 (LOQ)
Citalopram	0.154	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Clofibric acid	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Cyclobenzaprine	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Cyclophosphamide	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)

Parameter	UF	O3	BAC	RO
Diazepam	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Diclofenac	3.560	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Enalapril	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Fluoxetine	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Flutamide	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Furosemide	0.891	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Gabapentin	1.110	0.382	0.322	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Gemfibrozil	< 0.200 (LOQ)	< 0.200 (LOQ)	< 0.200 (LOQ)	< 0.200 (LOQ)
Hydrochlorothiazide	3.600	0.249	0.169	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Ifosfamide	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Indomethacin	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Iohexol	1.400	< 0.300 (LOQ)	< 0.300 (LOQ)	< 0.300 (LOQ)
Iomeprol	2.860	1.140	0.922	< 0.300 (LOQ)
Iopamidol	0.395	< 0.300 (LOQ)	< 0.300 (LOQ)	< 0.300 (LOQ)
Iopromide	4.860	1.880	1.320	< 0.300 (LOQ)
Ketoprofen	0.226	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Lincomycin	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Loperamide	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Metoprolol	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Metronidazole	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Mycophenolate mofetil	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Naproxen	0.214	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Oxazepam	0.228	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Paclitaxel	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Paracetamol (acetaminophen)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Piroxicam	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Propranolol	0.107	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Salbutamol	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Sertraline	0.130	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Sotalol	0.264	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Sulfamethazine	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Sulfamethoxazole	0.926	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Terbutaline	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Thebaine	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Tramadol	0.850	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Trimethoprim	0.141	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Valsartan	1.410	0.261	0.185	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Warfarin	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Zolpidem	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Estrogenic hormones (µg/L)				
17-β-estradiol	< 0.500 (LOQ)	< 0.500 (LOQ)	< 0.500 (LOQ)	< 5.00 (LOQ)
17-α-ethinylestradiol	< 0.050 (LOQ)	< 0.050 (LOQ)	< 0.050 (LOQ)	< 0.050 (LOQ)
Bisphenol A (µg/L)	< 0.050 (LOQ)	< 0.050 (LOQ)	< 0.050 (LOQ)	< 0.050 (LOQ)

Parameter	UF	O3	BAC	RO
Alkylphenols (µg/L)				
4-n-Octylphenol	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
4-Nonylphenol	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
4-t-Octylphenol	< 0.015 (LOQ)	< 0.010 (LOQ)	< 0.010 (LOQ)	< 0.010 (LOQ)
4-t-Octylphenol diethoxylate	< 0.010 (LOQ)	< 0.010 (LOQ)	< 0.010 (LOQ)	< 0.010 (LOQ)
4-t-Octylphenol monoethoxylate	< 0.010 (LOQ)	< 0.010 (LOQ)	< 0.010 (LOQ)	< 0.010 (LOQ)
4-t-Octylphenol triethoxylate	< 0.010 (LOQ)	< 0.010 (LOQ)	< 0.010 (LOQ)	< 0.010 (LOQ)
Nonylphenol (isomer mixture)	< 0.180 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Nonylphenol diethoxylate (isomer mixture)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Nonylphenol monoethoxylate (isomer mixture)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Nonylphenol triethoxylate (isomer mixture)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Sum of 5 OP and OPE	< 0.145 (LOQ)	< 0.140 (LOQ)	< 0.140 (LOQ)	< 0.140 (LOQ)
Sum of 4 NP and NPE	< 0.40 (LOQ)	< 0.40 (LOQ)	< 0.40 (LOQ)	< 0.40 (LOQ)
Sum of 5 NP and NPE	< 0.580 (LOQ)	< 0.500 (LOQ)	< 0.500 (LOQ)	< 0.500 (LOQ)
PFAS (ng/L)				
Perfluorobutane sulfonic acid (PFBS)	< 2.10 (LOQ)	1.74	1.41	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluorobutanoic acid (PFBA)	< 14.0 (LOQ)	6.6	7.1	< 2.0 (LOQ)
Perfluorodecane sulfonic acid (PFDS)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluorodecanoic acid (PFDA)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	0.33	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluorododecane sulfonic acid (PFDoDS)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluorododecanoic acid (PFDoDA)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluoroheptane sulfonic acid (PFHpS)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluoroheptanoic acid (PFHpA)	2.44	2.76	2.73	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluorohexane sulfonic acid (PFHxS)	0.98	0.96	0.73	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluorohexanoic acid (PFHxA)	5.89	6.73	6.73	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluorononane sulfonic acid (PFNS)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluorononanoic acid (PFNA)	0.5	0.56	0.45	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluorooctane sulfonic acid (PFOS)	1.68	2.05	1.28	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA)	4.12	3.44	2.7	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluoropentane sulfonic acid (PFPeS)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluoropentanoic acid (PFPeA)	5.32	7.61	7.33	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluorotridecane sulfonic acid (PFTrDS)	< 1.0 (LOQ)	< 1.0 (LOQ)	< 1.0 (LOQ)	< 1.0 (LOQ)
Perfluorotridecanoic acid (PFTrDA)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluoroundecane sulfonic acid (PFUnDS)	< 1.0 (LOQ)	< 1.0 (LOQ)	< 1.0 (LOQ)	< 1.0 (LOQ)
Perfluoroundecanoic acid (PFUnDA)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Sum of 20 PFAS (2020/2184)	20.9	32.8	30.5	< 9.10 (LOQ)
Bromides (mg/L)	0.254	0.259	0.257	< 0.050 (LOQ)
Bromates (µg/L)	< 3.0 (LOQ)	< 3.0 (LOQ)	< 3.0 (LOQ)	< 3.0 (LOQ)
Chlorates (µg/L)	23.1	< 8.0 (LOQ)	< 8.0 (LOQ)	< 8.0 (LOQ)
Chlorites (µg/L)	< 5.0 (LOQ)	< 5.0 (LOQ)	< 5.0 (LOQ)	< 5.0 (LOQ)
NDMA (ng/L)	< 3.60 (LOQ)	13.5	16.6	8.4
THM (µg/L)				
Bromodichloromethane	< 0.10 (LOQ)	< 0.10 (LOQ)	< 0.10 (LOQ)	< 0.10 (LOQ)
Bromoform	< 0.20 (LOQ)	< 0.20 (LOQ)	< 0.20 (LOQ)	< 0.20 (LOQ)

Parameter	UF	O3	BAC	RO
Chloroform	0.38	0.39	0.31	< 0.10 (LOQ)
Dibromochloromethane	< 0.10 (LOQ)	< 0.10 (LOQ)	< 0.10 (LOQ)	< 0.10 (LOQ)
Trihalomethanes - Total	0.38	0.39	0.31	< 0.50 (LOQ)
HAA (µg/L)				
Bromochloroacetic Acid	< 20.0 (LOQ)	< 20.0 (LOQ)	< 20.0 (LOQ)	< 20.0 (LOQ)
Bromodichloroacetic Acid	< 5.00 (LOQ)	< 5.00 (LOQ)	< 5.00 (LOQ)	< 5.00 (LOQ)
Dibromoacetic Acid	< 5.00 (LOQ)	< 5.00 (LOQ)	< 5.00 (LOQ)	< 5.00 (LOQ)
Dibromochloroacetic Acid	< 5.00 (LOQ)	< 5.00 (LOQ)	< 5.00 (LOQ)	< 5.00 (LOQ)
Dichloroacetic Acid	< 5.00 (LOQ)	< 5.00 (LOQ)	< 5.00 (LOQ)	< 5.00 (LOQ)
Monobromoacetic Acid	< 10.0 (LOQ)	< 10.0 (LOQ)	< 10.0 (LOQ)	< 10.0 (LOQ)
Monochloroacetic Acid	< 10.0 (LOQ)	< 10.0 (LOQ)	< 10.0 (LOQ)	< 10.0 (LOQ)
Tribromoacetic Acid	< 50.0 (LOQ)	< 50.0 (LOQ)	< 50.0 (LOQ)	< 50.0 (LOQ)
Trichloroacetic Acid	< 5.00 (LOQ)	< 5.00 (LOQ)	< 5.00 (LOQ)	< 5.00 (LOQ)
Sum of 5 HAAs	< 10.0 (LOQ)	< 10.0 (LOQ)	< 10.0 (LOQ)	< 10.0 (LOQ)
Sum of 9 HAAs	< 50.0 (LOQ)	< 50.0 (LOQ)	< 50.0 (LOQ)	< 50.0 (LOQ)
Sum of Chloroacetic Acids	< 10.0 (LOQ)	< 10.0 (LOQ)	< 10.0 (LOQ)	< 10.0 (LOQ)
A254 average [min, max] (cm⁻¹)	0.1428 [0.1090, 0.1663]	0.1048 [0.0476, 0.1505]	0.0918 [0.0431, 0.1371]	0.0015 [< 0.0001, 0.0155]
A436 average [min, max] (cm⁻¹)	0.0123 [0.0087, 0.0151]	0.0088 [< 0.0001, 0.0244]	0.0056 [< 0.0001, 0.0118]	0.0009 [< 0.0001, 0.0102]
TOC average [min, max] (mg C/L)	4.32 [2.59, 5.84]	4.20 [2.59, 5.84]	3.78 [2.32, 4.66]	0.21 [0.11, 0.27]
DOC average [min, max] (mg C/L)	4.32 [2.59, 5.84]	4.20 [2.59, 5.84]	3.78 [2.32, 4.66]	0.21 [0.11, 0.27]
EC @ 20°C average [min, max] (mS/cm)	1.171 [0.492, 3.830]	0.914 [0.502, 1.719]	0.885 [0.498, 1.476]	0.014 [0.010, 0.023]
pH average [min, max] (-)	7.1 [6.9, 7.2]	7.3 [7.0, 9.0]	7.0 [6.7, 7.3]	5.3 [5.1, 5.6]
Transmittance average [min, max] (%)	72.5 [68.2, 78.6]	79.1 [71.3, 91.7]	81.4 [73.8, 92.1]	99.9 [99.2, 100.0]
Turbidity average [min, max] (NTU)	0.06 [0.01, 0.30]	0.16 [0.01, 0.80]	0.10 [0.01, 0.51]	0.01 [0.01, 0.03]
Ammoniacal Nitrogen average [min, max] (mg NH₄/L)	5.27 [< 0.031, 19.00]	4.07 [< 0.031, 11.00]	3.21 [< 0.031, 15.00]	0.09 [< 0.031, 0.28]
Nitrates average [min, max] (mg NO₃/L)	18.52 [< 4.00, 30.00]	22.00 [12.00, 33.00]	21.46 [12.00, 33.00]	< 4.00 (LOQ)
Kjeldahl Nitrogen average [min, max] (mg N/L)	4.30 [< 0.500, 12.00]	3.92 [< 0.500, 12.00]	2.66 [< 0.500, 8.90]	< 0.500 (LOQ)
Total Nitrogen average [min, max] (mg N/L)	10.46 [5.70, 18.00]	10.24 [5.70, 18.00]	10.29 [6.10, 17.00]	0.53 [< 0.500, 0.73]
Total Phosphorus average [min, max] (mg P/L)	1.84 [0.07, 3.80]	1.86 [0.08, 3.90]	2.04 [0.57, 4.20]	< 0.020 (LOQ)

Parameter	UF	O3	BAC	RO
<i>Escherichia coli</i> (MPN/100 mL)	0	<i>n.a.</i>	0	0
<i>Clostridium perfringens</i> (CFU/100 mL)	0	0	0	0
<i>Clostridium perfringens</i> spores (CFU/50 mL)	0	0	0	0
Somatic coliphages (PFU/mL)	< 1 (LOQ)	< 1 (LOQ)	< 1 (LOQ)	< 1 (LOQ)
F-specific RNA bacteriophages (PFU/mL)	< 1 (LOQ)	< 1 (LOQ)	< 1 (LOQ)	< 1 (LOQ)
Ecotoxicology (%)				
Daphnia magna Immobilization (original sample)	6.7	20	0	8.3
<i>Vibrio fischeri</i> Inhibition for dilution 800 mL/L	29.5	19.5	16.1	10.8

n.a. - not measured; < - indicates a below LOQ value

Table I.4 – Main analytical results of potable reuse scheme 4 (outlet concentrations of each treatment process).

Parameter	SF	O3	BAC	RO
PhC (µg/L)				
Anastrozole	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Atenolol	0.123	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Azathioprine	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Bezafibrate	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Buprenorphine	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Butorphanol	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Caffeine	< 0.200 (LOQ)	< 0.200 (LOQ)	< 0.200 (LOQ)	< 0.200 (LOQ)
Capecitabine	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Carbamazepine	0.335	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Chloramphenicol	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Ciprofloxacin	0.995	< 0.600 (LOQ)	< 0.600 (LOQ)	< 0.600 (LOQ)
Citalopram	0.226	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Clofibric acid	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Cyclobenzaprine	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Cyclophosphamide	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Diazepam	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Diclofenac	2.380	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Enalapril	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Fluoxetine	0.242	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Flutamide	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Furosemide	1.280	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Gabapentin	1.140	0.340	0.299	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Gemfibrozil	< 0.200 (LOQ)	< 0.200 (LOQ)	< 0.200 (LOQ)	< 0.200 (LOQ)
Hydrochlorothiazide	1.960	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Ifosfamide	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Indomethacin	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Iohexol	0.921	0.398	0.435	< 0.300 (LOQ)

Parameter	SF	O3	BAC	RO
Iomeprol	2.350	1.200	1.180	< 0.300 (LOQ)
Iopamidol	< 0.600 (LOQ)	< 0.600 (LOQ)	< 0.600 (LOQ)	< 0.600 (LOQ)
Iopromide	1.510	0.764	0.740	< 0.300 (LOQ)
Ketoprofen	0.108	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Lincomycin	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Loperamide	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Metoprolol	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Metronidazole	0.111	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Mycophenolate mofetil	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Naproxen	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Oxazepam	0.228	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Paclitaxel	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Paracetamol (acetaminophen)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Piroxicam	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Propranolol	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Salbutamol	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Sertraline	0.204	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Sotalol	0.250	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Sulfamethazine	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Sulfamethoxazole	0.330	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Terbutaline	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Thebaine	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Tramadol	0.556	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Trimethoprim	0.152	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Valsartan	0.710	0.198	0.178	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Warfarin	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Zolpidem	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Estrogenic hormones (µg/L)				
17-β-estradiol	< 0.050 (LOQ)	< 0.050 (LOQ)	< 0.050 (LOQ)	< 0.050 (LOQ)
17-α-ethinylestradiol	< 0.050 (LOQ)	< 0.050 (LOQ)	< 0.050 (LOQ)	< 0.050 (LOQ)
Bisphenol A (µg/L)	0.076	<0.050 (LOQ)	0.145	<0.050 (LOQ)
Alkylphenols (µg/L)				
4-n-Octylphenol	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
4-Nonylphenol	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
4-t-Octylphenol	< 0.010 (LOQ)	< 0.010 (LOQ)	< 0.010 (LOQ)	< 0.010 (LOQ)
4-t-Octylphenol diethoxylate	< 0.010 (LOQ)	< 0.010 (LOQ)	< 0.010 (LOQ)	< 0.010 (LOQ)
4-t-Octylphenol monoethoxylate	< 0.010 (LOQ)	< 0.010 (LOQ)	< 0.010 (LOQ)	< 0.010 (LOQ)
4-t-Octylphenol triethoxylate	< 0.010 (LOQ)	< 0.010 (LOQ)	< 0.010 (LOQ)	< 0.010 (LOQ)
Nonylphenol (isomer mixture)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Nonylphenol diethoxylate (isomer mixture)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Nonylphenol monoethoxylate (isomer mixture)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Nonylphenol triethoxylate (isomer mixture)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)	< 0.100 (LOQ)
Sum of 5 OP and OPE	< 0.140 (LOQ)	< 0.140 (LOQ)	< 0.140 (LOQ)	< 0.140 (LOQ)

Parameter	SF	O3	BAC	RO
Sum of 4 NP and NPE	< 0.40 (LOQ)	< 0.40 (LOQ)	< 0.40 (LOQ)	< 0.40 (LOQ)
Sum of 5 NP and NPE	< 0.500 (LOQ)	< 0.500 (LOQ)	< 0.500 (LOQ)	< 0.500 (LOQ)
PFAS (ng/L)				
Perfluorobutane sulfonic acid (PFBS)	3.13	3.60	3.73	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluorobutanoic acid (PFBA)	< 16.0 (LOQ)	8.60	9.30	< 2.0 (LOQ)
Perfluorodecane sulfonic acid (PFDS)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluorodecanoic acid (PFDA)	0.42	0.40	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluorododecane sulfonic acid (PFDoDS)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluorododecanoic acid (PFDoDA)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluoroheptane sulfonic acid (PFHpS)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluoroheptanoic acid (PFHpA)	4.07	4.98	4.79	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluorohexane sulfonic acid (PFHxS)	2.10	2.09	1.92	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluorohexanoic acid (PFHxA)	9.22	10.40	10.40	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluorononane sulfonic acid (PFNS)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluorononanoic acid (PFNA)	1.23	1.44	1.06	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluorooctane sulfonic acid (PFOS)	3.00	3.23	2.49	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA)	8.75	7.22	6.53	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluoropentane sulfonic acid (PFPeS)	0.64	0.38	0.32	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluoropentanoic acid (PFPeA)	10.20	13.50	12.90	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluorotridecane sulfonic acid (PFTrDS)	< 1.0 (LOQ)	< 1.0 (LOQ)	< 1.0 (LOQ)	< 1.0 (LOQ)
Perfluorotridecanoic acid (PFTrDA)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Perfluoroundecane sulfonic acid (PFUnDS)	< 1.0 (LOQ)	< 1.0 (LOQ)	< 1.0 (LOQ)	< 1.0 (LOQ)
Perfluoroundecanoic acid (PFUnDA)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)	< 0.30 (LOQ)
Sum of 20 PFAS (2020/2184)	42.80	55.80	53.40	< 9.10 (LOQ)
Bromides (mg/L)	1.49	1.45	1.47	< 0.050 (LOQ)
Bromates (µg/L)	< 9.0 (LOQ)	< 9.0 (LOQ)	< 9.0 (LOQ)	< 3.0 (LOQ)
Chlorates (µg/L)	< 8.0 (LOQ)	< 8.0 (LOQ)	< 8.0 (LOQ)	< 8.0 (LOQ)
Chlorites (µg/L)	< 5.0 (LOQ)	< 5.0 (LOQ)	< 5.0 (LOQ)	< 5.0 (LOQ)
NDMA (ng/L)	1.67	<i>n.a.</i>	<i>n.a.</i>	5.61
THM (µg/L)				
Bromodichloromethane	< 0.10 (LOQ)	< 0.10 (LOQ)	< 0.10 (LOQ)	< 0.10 (LOQ)
Bromoform	< 0.20 (LOQ)	10.20	4.22	0.26
Chloroform	0.41	0.52	0.45	0.13
Dibromochloromethane	< 0.10 (LOQ)	0.17	< 0.10 (LOQ)	< 0.10 (LOQ)
Trihalomethanes - Total	0.41	10.90	4.67	0.39
HAA (µg/L)				
Bromochloroacetic Acid	< 2.0 (LOQ)	< 2.0 (LOQ)	< 2.0 (LOQ)	< 2.0 (LOQ)
Bromodichloroacetic Acid	< 0.50 (LOQ)	< 0.50 (LOQ)	< 0.50 (LOQ)	< 0.50 (LOQ)
Dibromoacetic Acid	< 0.50 (LOQ)	1.64	0.65	< 0.50 (LOQ)
Dibromochloroacetic Acid	< 0.50 (LOQ)	< 0.50 (LOQ)	< 0.50 (LOQ)	< 0.50 (LOQ)
Dichloroacetic Acid	< 0.50 (LOQ)	< 0.50 (LOQ)	< 0.50 (LOQ)	< 0.50 (LOQ)
Monobromoacetic Acid	< 1.0 (LOQ)	1.40	< 1.0 (LOQ)	< 1.0 (LOQ)
Monochloroacetic Acid	< 3.5 (LOQ)	< 3.0 (LOQ)	< 3.5 (LOQ)	< 1.0 (LOQ)

Parameter	SF	O3	BAC	RO
Tribromoacetic Acid	< 5.0 (LOQ)	< 5.0 (LOQ)	< 5.0 (LOQ)	< 5.0 (LOQ)
Trichloroacetic Acid	0.79	0.89	0.66	< 0.50 (LOQ)
Sum of 5 HAAs	< 2.0 (LOQ)	< 2.0 (LOQ)	< 2.0 (LOQ)	< 1.0 (LOQ)
Sum of 9 HAAs	< 5.0 (LOQ)	< 5.0 (LOQ)	< 5.0 (LOQ)	< 5.0 (LOQ)
Sum of Chloroacetic Acids	< 3.5 (LOQ)	< 3.5 (LOQ)	< 3.5 (LOQ)	< 1.0 (LOQ)
A254 average [min, max] (cm-1)	0.1677 [0.1600, 0.1753]	0.04275 [0.0065, 0.0790]	0.0628 [0.0581, 0.0702]	< 0.0001 (LOQ)
A436 average [min, max] (cm-1)	0.0138	0.0008	0.0016 [< 0.0001, 0.0032]	< 0.0001 (LOQ)
TOC average [min, max] (mg C/L)	6.43 [5.32, 7.00]	6.44 [5.20, 7.20]	5.65 [4.52, 6.39]	0.13 [0.06, 0.22]
DOC average [min, max] (mg C/L)	6.30 [5.12, 7.00]	6.45 [5.25, 7.20]	5.71 [4.70, 6.39]	0.13 [0.06, 0.22]
EC @ 20°C average [min, max] (mS/cm)	1.111 [0.720, 1.773]	1.110 [0.712, 1.792]	1.224 [0.698, 1.790]	0.018 [0.016, 0.021]
pH average [min, max] (-)	7.2 [7.0, 7.4]	7.2 [7.1, 7.3]	7.2 [6.9, 7.3]	5.3 [5.2, 5.4]
Transmittance average [min, max] (%)	68.9 [65.9, 71.6]	85.3 [83.6, 86.3]	86.7 [85.7, 87.6]	100.0
Turbidity average [min, max] (NTU)	0.50 [0.20, 0.80]	0.27 [0.13, 0.40]	0.10 [0.04, 0.15]	0.01 [0.01, 0.01]
Ammoniacal Nitrogen average [min, max] (mg NH ₄ /L)	8.53 [1.13, 12.00]	3.41 [0.24, 9.60]	7.91 [2.54, 13.70]	0.27 [0.137, 0.41]
Nitrates average [min, max] (mg NO ₃ /L)	14.23 [7.70, 15.20]	15.06 [5.99, 20.70]	23.83 [15.20, 30.00]	< 4.00 (LOQ)
Kjeldahl Nitrogen average [min, max] (mg N/L)	7.92 [0.68, 14.00]	9.70 [6.30, 13.90]	5.66 [2.67, 9.30]	< 0.500 (LOQ)
Total Nitrogen average [min, max] (mg N/L)	12.23 [7.70, 15.20]	13.43 [11.30, 15.50]	12.47 [10.00, 14.30]	0.59 [0.52, 0.64]
Total Phosphorus average [min, max] (mg P/L)	2.72 [1.26, 4.64]	2.39 [1.05, 3.28]	2.80 [1.45, 3.65]	< 0.020 (LOQ)
Escherichia coli average [min, max] (MPN/100 mL)	3.9x10 ³ [1.3x10 ³ , 8.1x10 ³]	<i>n.a.</i>	12 [1, 23]	0
Clostridium perfringens (CFU/100 mL)	610	800	14	0
Clostridium perfringens spores (CFU/50 mL)	220	520	0	0
Somatic coliphages (PFU/mL)	< 1 (LOQ)	< 1 (LOQ)	< 1 (LOQ)	< 1 (LOQ)
F-specific RNA bacteriophages (PFU/mL)	< 1 (LOQ)	< 1 (LOQ)	< 1 (LOQ)	< 1 (LOQ)
Ecotoxicology (%)				
Daphnia magna Immobilization (original sample)	0	0	0	0
Vibrio fischeri Inhibition for dilution 800 mL/L	13.7	15.5	10.3	14.5

n.a. - not measured; < - indicates a below LOQ value

